

AI4DI Artificial Intelligence for Digitizing Industry

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1 Executive summary

In recent decades, research in the field of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has made significant progress in developing models that are capable of generalising on multiple tasks. This new versatility can be seen as the cornerstone for industrial adoption of AI as a narrow, rule-based system can be replaced by more general methodologies.

Recently emerging models in the field of machine learning are data-driven as the algorithms learn to detect characteristic patterns in vast data sets to recognise the same pattern in new, unseen scenarios. Examples of successful industrial applications are predictive maintenance, anomaly detection, autonomous driving, e-commerce, robotic control, or process scheduling.

The need for huge sets of training data has become a bottleneck for many applications. Hence, a common trend is to artificially create data sets, e.g. by simulating a specific scenario. It is worth noting that simulations are used in industry for decades in a wide variety of different applications, such as computational fluid dynamics for evaluating physical quantities in fluids or testing scenarios to evaluate the best outcome for a management decision on micro- and macroscopic level.

Cutting-edge AI methods, combined with an abundant amount of data generated from simulations, have the potential to disrupt inefficient processes and may lead to a significant competitive edge in the industrial sector.

This report gives an overview of the simulation and modelling approaches at the system and subsystem level for the integration of AI methods across different supply chains within the AI4DI project.

The report starts with a short introduction regarding simulation where benefits and shortcomings are critically discussed. A high-level overview of the use-cases of each of the contributing partners is presented. The report covers four industrial sectors: Automotive Industry (Chapter 5), Machinery (Chapter 6), Food and Beverage Industry (Chapter 7) and Transportation Industry (Chapter 8) are addressed in individual chapters.

2 Publishable summary

The same content as the "Executive Summary".

3 Non publishable information

N/A

4 Introduction & Scope

As defined in [1], a simulation is an approximate imitation of the operation of a process or system. Simulations are nowadays an essential part of many branches in industry and science. For example, simulations are the main tool in meteorology for weather forecasting [2], an essential part of financial market analysis [3], or a safe approach of evaluating virus spreading in time of pandemics [4].

Semantically, the term simulation is very closely linked to the term modelling, where modelling is the act of conceptual representation of a system, while simulation is the execution of that model, i.e., its transient behaviour. When people talk about simulations, they usually think of computer simulations, where a real system or process is first described in terms of mathematical, physical, logical or other formalisms, and then translated to an assembly language in order to be executed on a machine. With the recent advances of hardware and software R&D, complex processes and systems can be modelled and simulated reliably, which makes simulation such an important and wide-spread tool. Some of the advantages of running simulations instead of relying on the real systems and processes are the following:

- **Reduced costs:** The simulation of a system is a very cost-effective alternative to the actual system regarding the purpose of analysing characteristics. This is usually the motivation of using simulation for manufacturing systems in industry. As stated in [5], using the actual system of a production plant for performance analysis might be disruptive for the production process. Moreover, changes/extensions of the system are significantly more cost-efficient to implement in a simulation than on the real system.
- **Non-feasible alternatives:** In many cases, the system under consideration is impractical to be tested directly. An intuitive example are space exploration projects: Testing a planetary rover for operation on Mars by sending it there and getting results is very expensive and highly impractical, compared to simulating the rover and the conditions on the planet and then using the simulation data for analysis and improvements. Another example is given by the analysis of nuclear wars [6].
- **Safety:** Frequently, simulations provide additional safety over direct usage of the actual system. One of the most common applications is training, for example training of pilots on highly-realistic simulators before training with an actual airplane [7], or virtual-reality simulations of surgery in medicine [8].
- **Time as a parameter:** In simulations, time is just a parameter that needs to be chosen. Consider that simulating fluid dynamics or Newtonian physics might require time scales in the magnitude order of nanoseconds. To the contrary, simulating star constellations [9] or the origin of the universe [10], temporal resolutions are usually in the magnitude order of millennia. Note, one of the obvious benefits of simulations is that time can be accelerated (faster than real time) and important predictions can be made on future effects, for example using Susceptible-Infected-Recovered (SIR) models [4] to determine effects of infectious disease spreading in order to develop governmental strategies and to measure how spreading can be suppressed.

While simulations offer obvious benefits over using the real systems, the simulation models are still an abstraction of the real system or process. Thus, special care has to be taken in order to ensure that the simulation and its results are valid for the intended purpose. Some of the usual shortcomings of using simulations are as follows:

- Incorrect modelling:** Representing a complex real system as a model is a challenging and time-consuming task that requires high degree of understanding of the actual system or process as well as modelling techniques in the fields of mathematics, statistics, physics, logics or similar, as indicated in [5]. The environment is often subject to significant simplifications like continuous real-world processes that are usually modelled using discrete time-steps to be able to solve sets of ordinary differential equations. This is, among others, a common approach for physics simulators in robotics where the physical processes like collisions are simulated by calculations based on temporal discretization, where precision increases by reducing time resolution. The necessity to validate simulations that are subject to significant simplifications is obvious. Different approaches for verifying and validating simulations can be found in [11]. A well-known aphorism from George Box [12] states that “all models are wrong but some models are useful” and this reflects the issues that arise when developing models for industry-relevant tasks and processes: the model should be useful and precise enough for the intended purpose.
- Parameterization:** Even when the computational model is valid, simulations tend to be very sensitive to configurable settings such as initial conditions, boundary conditions and model parameters. While this can be an advantage in order to explore how a real system would behave under different configurations, it becomes an issue when the simulation is intended to precisely imitate the real-world process. Determining the correct settings might require additional experimenting, sensitivity analysis or expert knowledge, which complicates the usage of the simulation as well as the interpretation and usability of the simulation results. One approach for identifying acceptable values for the simulation parameters is to perform statistical tests where the simulation and the real system outputs for the same inputs are compared. Then, the parameters can be fine-tuned until there is no significant difference between the simulation and the real system outputs.
- Adoption:** Simulation tools are often difficult to use due to the complexity of the systems they are modelling, the unintuitive interfaces for developing the simulation, as well as the fact that sometimes the users do not have the required expert knowledge to correctly model and parameterize the simulation. This is a frequently occurring problem in manufacturing, as indicated in [5]. Furthermore, as simulations are often developed and valid for a very specific use case, their reusability is limited and hence cost inefficient/impractical.

advanced manufacturing technologies	United States	China	Europe	Sum
predictive analytics	1	1	4	6
smart factories (IoT)	4	2	1	7
smart, connected products (IoT)	2	7	2	11
advanced materials	3	4	5	12
digital design, simulation, and integration	5	5	3	13
high performance computing	6	3	7	16
advanced robotics	7	8	6	21
augmented reality (to improve quality, training, expert knowledge)	10	6	8	24
additive manufacturing (3D Printing)	8	11	9	27
open-source design / direct customer input	9	10	10	29
augmented reality (to increase customer service & experience)	11	9	11	31

source: Deloitte survey of 500 global senior manufacturing executives, 2016

 t2.3 is a perfect fit here
 t2.3 is a quite good fit here

FIGURE 1: RANKING OF ADVANCED MANUFACTURING TECHNOLOGIES BY IMPORTANCE (ADAPTED FROM [13]).

Despite some of the abovementioned shortcomings of using simulations in the industrial context, a recent study [13] clearly indicated that the simulations are one of the most important tools that will drive innovation and unlock new opportunities for industries in the future. Figure 1: shows the result of a survey from this study in relation to the scope of the AI4DI Task 2.3 that is reported in this deliverable. In general, the work carried out under Task 2.3 by different AI4DI partners is very well aligned with the current trends in the industry and covers some of the most important advanced manufacturing technologies.

In the next sections of the report, we first give a high-level overview covering the specific use-cases of each of the partners involved in this report. Afterwards, the four supply chains covered by Task 2.3 are addressed in separate chapters, where each partner involved within the supply chain provides a detailed overview of their specific activities. Finally, a conclusion chapter summarizes the contributions of this report to the overall picture and the relation to the next work packages and tasks.

4.1 Purpose and target group

The purpose of this report is to provide a detailed overview on the activities each partner carried out in Task 2.3 on hybrid intelligent system and sub-system level modelling and simulation for integration of AI methods, in order to identify tools, approaches and synergies between partners to facilitate the implementation within the different supply chains. For that purpose, the partners were asked to provide a mapping of their use cases according to the following criteria:

- **Level:** What is the level of the process/use case the partner is working on (system or sub-system) level?
- **Deployment:** Where is the solution going to be deployed: (edge, cloud, or at their interface)?
- **AI methodology:** Which AI-based methods are planned to be used in the solution?
- **Challenge:** What is the challenge that the proposed solution should solve by employing AI methods?
- **Simulation tools:** Which tools for simulation and modelling are going to be used/adopted?

The results of the high-level mapping are presented in Table 1. Detailed information about each partner's activities is provided in separate section.

TABLE 1 GENERAL OVERVIEW OF THE PARTNERS' USE CASES W.R.T. THE TARGETED LEVEL, DEPLOYMENT, AI METHODOLOGY APPLIED, THE AI CHALLENGE ADRESSED AND THE SIMULATION TOOLS USED.

	Level		Deployment			AI Methodology	AI Challenge	Simulation Tools
	System	Sub System	Edge	Edge to Cloud	Cloud	Supervised, Unsupervised, Reinforcement Learning	Reasoning, Planning, Learning, NLP, Perception, Motion and Manipulation, Social Intelligence	Software Tools, Libraries, Platforms
TUM		Automotive Manufacturing Cell	Control		Training, Simulation	Reinforcement Learning	Learning, Manipulation	Unity
TUG	Autonomous Systems		Monitoring & Diagnosis			Model-based Reasoning	Combining the physical world with logic-based reasoning. Utilizing simulation models for diagnostic reasoning	ASP & other logic theorem prover, non-monotonic reasoning extensions, simulators based on Modelica
OTH		Data processing in ITS	Partitioning Scheduling		Training, Simulation	Reinforcement Learning	Planning	SUMO, SimGrid
VAISTO		Industrial work machines: Tractor and log forwarder trailer and indoor logistics robots	Work machine edge computer		Training, Simulation	Reinforcement Learning	Learning, Perception, Motion and Manipulation	Unity with ML-Agents
TUD		Industrial robots	Edge signal processing	Wireless data exchange of recognized events		Dimension reduction methods (PCA, IIR FILTER, Mutual information, Temporal CNN) as well as Deep learning models (DNN, CNN-LSTM, LOW PASS LSTM)	Distinction between different event criticalities as well as overall process latency times	TensorFlow 2.0 and Keras
ITML		Material Planning Decision Support System	Data collection		Decision Support	Supervised	Learning, prediction	Data Fusion Bus

INTRA		Communication platform for digital twins	Data collection		Data management			
BUT		Electric drives	Real time condition monitoring, motor control efficiency optimization		Training, simulation	Supervised learning, Deep learning, Reinforcement learning	Reasoning, perception, motion	MATLAB Simulink, GoogLeNet, AURIX, NVidia
BUT		Autonomous mobile robotic agent for industrial transportation	Petri planning, Navigation, Mapping	Robot Localization	Resource planning, Environment map management	Reinforcement learning	Learning, Path Planning, Behavioural prediction	ROS, Rviz, Unity
AVL	Autonomous vehicle systems		Monitoring & Diagnosis			Model-based Reasoning, unsupervised learning, supervised learning Deep learning	Combining physical-knowledge and data-based reasoning for real-time failure prediction	MATLAB Simulink, Simulation tools (TensorFlow, TPU)
SINTEF IGT NXTECH	Production process optimization	Moisture pre-processing (P2)	Real-time condition monitoring, Data collection, Edge computing		Training	AI modelling, Machine learning, Deep learning methods, Image and multi-sensor processing methods, Pattern recognition methods.	Real-time image and multi-sensor connectivity, Parameter identification, Pattern recognition, Decision making based on AI algorithms	ROS, TensorFlow 2.0
SINTEF IGT NXTECH	Predictive maintenance	Hammer mill (M8)	Real-time condition monitoring, Data collection, Edge computing		Training	AI modelling, Machine learning, Deep learning methods, Multi-sensor processing methods, Pattern recognition methods.	Real-time multi-sensor connectivity, Parameter identification, Pattern recognition, Decision making based on AI algorithms	ROS, TensorFlow 2.0

4.2 Contributions of partners

Table 2 summarizes the individual contributions of each partner. In addition to the initially assigned partners for Task 2.3, VAISTO also contributed as their work was in line with the activities of this task.

TABLE 2: CONTRIBUTIONS

Chapter	Partner	Contribution
	TUM	Coordination and preparing of the report
Chapters 1, 2, 3, 4, 9	TUM	General chapters not related to the Supply Chains
Chapter 4	All partners	Input to Section 4.1
Chapter 5	TUM	Section 5.1.1
Chapter 5	BUT	Section 5.1.2
Chapter 5	INTRA	Section 5.1.3
Chapter 5	ITML	Section 5.1.4
Chapter 5	TUG, BUT, AVL	Section 5.2
Chapter 6	TUD	Section 6.1
Chapter 6	VAISTO	Section 6.2 and Section 8.1.2
Chapter 7	SINTEF/EGT/NXTECH	Section 7.1
Chapter 8	OTH	Introduction and Section 8.1.1

4.3 Relation to other activities in the project

The work carried out under task 2.3 and reported here has been founded on the functional and non-functional requirements indented in WP1. The activities reported here were closely coordinated with task 2.1 and Task 2.2 from WP2. In this direction, the report presents concepts and examples how different use-cases and demonstrators will be implemented using simulation and modelling tools following the system-level architecture defined in task 2.1 and the hardware and software partitioning defined in task 2.2 and how different AI tools will be integrated to produce hybrid-intelligent systems. The output of this report will be used as an input in the next work packages related to implementation, validation and standardization.

5 Automotive Industry

5.1 AI supported automotive manufacturing and logistics

5.1.1 AI supported automotive manufacturing (TUM)

The focus of this subtopic is the employment of advanced data-driven methods to control industrial manipulators that operate in automotive manufacturing cells. In this context, a manufacturing cell can be described as a subsystem within a heterogeneous production line according to the first key-target (KT-1) within the framework of the AI4DI project. Moreover, the in this section described solution is planned to be applied on a robotic-assisted manufacturing cell where an industrial manipulator is performing spot and arc welding on car bodies to foster higher productivity (due to near-optimal control) as well as versatility to adapt to a wide range of varying tasks [14]. Note, the performance of the employed data-driven methods, such as reinforcement learning (RL) introduced below, depends heavily on huge amount of data, which are tedious to be generated in the real world. Within the here described approach, data are gathered by digital twins interacting with simulated environments, which is a convenient way to generate an abundant amount of training data. For this purpose, the robotic-assisted manufacturing cell is modelled using an advanced game engine. During simulation, a RL algorithm learns to control the simulated robot to achieve an arbitrary task within the manufacturing environment.

The training of the controller occurs at the cloud side where the digital twin of the system is located. Furthermore, industrial automation requires real-time control; and this implies the necessity to transfer the trained control system from the cloud to the real system, the robotic manipulator in the real world, located at the edge.

As described in Table 1, the subtopic that is addressed by TUM is on the subsystem level, as we are working on a digital twin of a robotic manufacturing cell within the factory. Moreover, the solution will be located at the cloud as well as at the edge, because the training of the model will take place in the cloud, but the trained model will then be employed at the edge to control robotic manipulators in the manufacturing process. The employed AI methodology is mostly RL and the challenge is to learn robotic manipulation. Unity 3D [15] is used as a tool to simulate the real-world environment as introduced below.

5.1.1.1 Modelling

FIGURE 2: EXAMPLE OF AN AGENT INTERACTING WITH A GENERIC ENVIRONMENT.

The subtopic that will be covered by TUM incorporates a variety of different technologies. Regarding modelling, the central part within the tool chain is RL and is therefore subject of this section. In the following, a brief introduction to RL is provided; further details to this topic can be found in the educational material provided by Sutton and Barto [16] as well as Silver [17].

Figure 2 shows an agent interacting with a generic environment. The illustrated elements are described as follows:

- **environment & state:** The environment is a generic framework that fits to many different control problems. An important feature of the environment is the state S_t that holistically represents the dynamics of states evolving over time t . Note that the state is (partially) perceivable from outside of the environment to facilitate instances to infer the current state of the environment without being part of it.
- **reward:** In addition to the state, the environment provides a reward R_t . The reward assesses the current state by a single numerical signal. By associating scenarios with positive/negative rewards, an agent can learn to behave in an environment in the same way children learn to avoid pain (negative reward) or to maximize happiness (positive reward).
- **actions:** To interact with the environment, an agent can perform actions A_t to influence the future evolvement of states and thus the expected cumulated future reward. By doing so, the agent follows its goal to select actions in a way that state trajectories lead to a maximum amount of expected rewards in the future.
- **agent:** The agent acts according to a learned strategy based on the perceived states. In the learning phase, the agent approximates the action policy that finds A_t in a way that the accumulated future reward is maximized. In real-world problems, the states are usually high-dimensionally nested, leading to state spaces that exceeds the possibility to find optimal actions for every single state. It is hence a common approach to generalize states by non-linear function approximators (e.g. neural networks) to recognize the best policy for group of states that are similar to each other instead of evaluating a policy for every state.

FIGURE 3: EMPLOYING RL FOR CONTROLLING INDUSTRIAL ROBOTS IN PRODUCTION LINES IN THE AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY.

Figure 3 shows the application of RL in the subtopic that is addressed by TUM within the AI4DI framework. The agent controls an industrial robot in order to achieve goals that are relevant in an industrial context like welding, drilling or picking & placing objects. Depending on the actual use case, the environment could represent a production line or a single production cell in the automotive industry. In order to perceive the current situation, the state representation can be in the form of camera signals or numerical representations like the angle and/or angular speed of the robot's joints. Learning in the real world is not practical as the amount of experience that is necessary for evaluating a suitable policy is vast and long periods of try and error are usually required. The idea addressed in the following is to rebuild the agent as well as the environment in a simulation where learning can be

done efficiently in a highly parallelized way. Afterwards, the policy is transferred to the real world. More details to the simulation part as well as measures to deal with differences between simulation and the real world are emphasized in the next sections.

5.1.1.2 *Simulation*

In the context of employing digital twins for industrial tasks, a suitable simulation should be a task-related digital replica of the real-world process or system. This implies that the simulation is required to capture all relevant real-world phenomena needed to represent or solve the task of interest. In the context of automotive manufacturing, one example is given by the welding of a car body using a robotic manipulator. In this case, if the digital twin is used within an environment for RL training, it should correctly simulate the physical effects that occur due to the interaction between the welding robot and the car body. If learning is based on visual input, realistic graphical effects are required, like illumination of the welding sparks. Simulations of this type may become quite tedious and impractical to produce from scratch, due to the complexity of simulating the real-world phenomena with a high degree of precision.

As we will argue in the following, game engines are of particular interest for the approach described in this subtopic. While earlier video games, like the Atari 2600 console games [18], have been representing a two-dimensional pixelated simplification of the real-world, today's modern video games, like Control [19] or Call of Duty [20], are able to represent complex three-dimensional environments with highly realistic renderings and physics. The game engines that provide the tools for building such games, can be easily applied to accurately simulate the factory environment and the systems and subsystems involved in the manufacturing processes. In this way, much of the complexity in developing simulations is transferred to the game engine. Consequently, the simulation developer can focus on correctly parametrizing the digital twin instead of investing time in correct calculations of physical equations and ray-tracing technologies for producing photo-realistic renderings.

Unity 3D [15] is one of the most popular game engines available on the market, with state-of-art physics and rendering techniques integrated in its toolchains and pipelines for the creation of digital content. To provide fast and accurate physics calculations, Unity 3D is based on PhysX [21], which is a scalable and multi-platform GPU-accelerated physics solver developed by Nvidia. PhysX makes it possible to perform a large number of complex physics calculations in parallel with a high degree of accuracy. On the rendering side, Unity 3D provides several pipelines, from the built-in general-purpose rendering pipeline to the high definition rendering pipeline, allowing for creation of either simplified or highly realistic visuals even in real time.

For our use case, we employ Unity to provide the low-level physics and rendering capabilities, while shifting our focus to correctly creating and interfacing the digital twin of the manufacturing environment. For this purpose, we use three-dimensional models for rebuilding the environment, all objects as well as the robotic manipulator. In Unity for example, the links of the real robotic manipulator are simulated as detailed volumetric meshes that behave like rigid bodies. Parameters like mass, centre of mass or inertia tensor and other physical properties need to be provided for each link. Furthermore, the connections between all links are simulated as hinge joints, where parameters like rotational axis, rotational limits or break forces are required. This allows for precise configuration of the simulation environment, in a way that the digital twin trustworthy represents the real-world original.

With the simulation developed in Unity, interfaces can be created to read the state. For example, in our use case the state of the robotic manipulator can be described by the angles and the rotational speeds of each joint at any point in time. Note that these values are already provided by the hinge joint implementation in Unity, and an interface can be developed to publish these values in a desirable format (json, xml) for external applications. Beyond interfaces for reading data, the implementation of interfaces for controlling the digital twin is also possible. For example, in our use case, we can have an interface for setting the desired velocities or torques for each of the joints at any point of time, enabling to control the robot. These interfaces allow reading and updating the digital twin's state to develop applications for different purposes, like visualization and monitoring of the digital twin's state over time, or training of RL algorithms, using the simulation as a substitute for the expensive and impractical real-world training.

FIGURE 4 EXAMPLE OF A DIGITAL TWIN SIMULATION FOR ROBOTIC MANUFACTURING PROCESSES USING UNITY 3D. A) DIGITAL TWIN OF A IIWA-14 ROBOTIC MANIPULATOR FROM KUKA [22]. B) BIRD-VIEW PERSPECTIVE SHOWING A SIMULATION OF MULTIPLE MANIPULATORS IN PARALLEL. C) DIGITAL TWIN S SOLVING A COMPLEX WELDING TASK IN A HIGHLY REALISTIC RENDERED ENVIRONMENT

Three examples of the simulation environment of our use case developed in Unity are shown in Figure 4. Figure 4a shows the digital twin of the robotic manipulator in a simplified simulation environment. The simplified version still supports high-precision physics calculations but is not intended to provide highly realistic rendering. This is sufficient for training a RL agent when the system state is only described by the speeds and the angles of the manipulator's joints or the position of the end effector. With this approach, many digital twins can be simulated in parallel, as shown in Figure 4b, without a significant decrease of the simulation speed. However, if the system's state needs to be represented as an image from a vision sensor, one might need to simulate high-quality renderings to capture visual effects that would occur in the real world. Figure 4c demonstrates the simulation of complex lighting conditions, reflections, sparks or smoke that resemble the real-world effects appearing during a welding task.

5.1.1.3 *Real-world Deployment*

Training the control policy in a simulated environment not only provides a possibility to generate an abundant source of data, but also has the potential to avoid unsafe robot motions that might happen when training is done in the real world. However, one of the main challenges when the learning of the control policy is completely done in simulation is to transfer the trained controller from the simulation to the real world [23, 24].

Simplified simulation models and modelling errors cause the simulated system to not behave exactly as the physical system. Hence, due to the differences between the simulated environment and the real world, suitable control policies trained in simulation often fail to keep their performance when deployed in the real world.

FIGURE 5 EXISTENCE OF THE REALITY GAP WHEN TRANSFERRING THE LEARNED CONTROL POLICY FROM VIRTUAL WORLD TO REAL WORLD

The significance of this loss in industrial applications is obvious and therefore should be avoided. This problem is known as the *reality gap* illustrated in Figure 5. To reduce the *reality gap* several methods, exist. A few of the promising methods are as follows:

- **Increasing simulation accuracy:**
 - **Realistic physics:** Simulating physics of the real world as accurate as possible can reduce the reality gap. This can be achieved by employing advanced physics simulation engines such as Nvidia PhysX [21], which provides a way to simulate dynamics of rigid bodies and soft bodies in a three-dimensional space.
 - **Realistic rendering:** The possibility to have realistic rendering becomes of great importance when the state of the environment is observed by camera signals. Note that synthetic images can be generated by the high-definition rendering pipeline of Unity. An example of how to implement high-fidelity rendering in a similar context can be found in [25].
- **Increasing robustness of the control policy:** One reason for the control performance drop when it is transferred to the real world is arising from overfitting on virtual data in an ideal simulation environment. To reduce the effects of this issue, the simulation environment can be changed in a way that it deviates from the ideal model by adding intended random uncertainties to the system behaviour. As an implication of adding uncertainties, the learned control policy generalization is enhanced improving the real-world performance.
 - **Dynamics randomization:** The impact of actions on the environment is randomized by varying the simulation parameters representing dynamics/physics of the environment. Dynamics of the environment are modelled by the physics engine and are a function of material and system properties such as objects mass, inertia and centre of gravity, friction, and damping coefficients. The suitability of this approach is shown in [26] where the described methodology is applied to the control of a robotic arm that learns to push objects.
 - **Domain randomization:** The observations of the environment are randomized by varying the way the system is perceived. For instance, using pictures as observations, domain randomization can be implemented by randomly rendering the objects with unrealistic textures, at different locations and under different factors, e.g. different camera positions [27].

- **Compact observation space:** By reducing the dimensionality of the observation space, the learned action policy can easily avoid overfitting to unimportant details of the simulation, which does not exist in the real world [23].
- **Real world fine-tuning:** The control performance is further increased by continuing the learning process in the real world in order to let the RL agent adapt its behaviour with the new uncertain situations that has not been previously trained for [28, 29].

5.1.2 Modelling and simulation of mobile robotic agents for industrial transportation (BUT)

An integral part of industrial manufacturing process is a solution of transportation within the factory, dealing with convey of materials, components or completed subsystems of a final product. Among the most common conveyors of various type (overhead conveyors, lifting chain hangers, belt conveyors, assembly lines etc.), there is still many transportation needs solved by human-driven forklifts.

Such a solution brings into the whole system of automated or semi-automated production several drawbacks and critical points:

- **Risk of damage:** the human driven vehicles in industrial environments brings still much bigger probability of failure then computer driven vehicles. Consequences of such failures can lead to serious impact on production, safety, or economics.
- **Speed of transport:** Human-less transportation systems can usually work in much higher velocities keeping the probability of damage on low level.
- **Efficiency:** Autonomous vehicles can negotiate their pathways more easily and unambiguously, what leads to shorter ways without collisions. Such collisions are highly unwanted since they bring indeterministic transportation delay and increase risk of damage.
- **Reliability:** In simple and straightforward environments (as industrial halls can be), the routine operation of automated vehicles is more reliable since the often phenomenon of losing the concentration is eliminated in case of machines.
- **Nondeterminism:** Because of time stochastic characteristics of human work (same procedure usually does not take the same time), the time planning is much complicated and finally less optimal then in case if only time-deterministic machines are used.
- **Space waste:** there is a necessity of wide pathways allowing safe driving without danger of hitting the surrounding obstacles.

It is clear from the list above, that removing the component of human-driven forklift from the production chain is highly required step in a way to smooth and safe production; and the benefits of doing so are much more important than only saving human resources, as is often misrepresented in the media. It brings higher efficiency, throughput, and safety with reducing the operational costs in a same time.

As a result of this, this subtopic is dealing with a development of semi-autonomous mobile robotic agent capable of independent transportation of goods or technologies within the known environment of industrial production hall.

Despite the fact that the environment is basically static and its map in known in advance, there are several dynamic situations, which each of such mobile robotic agent must be able to solve out without any damage or a significant delay in a terms of production output. For example:

- Human operator steps into the way of robotic agent.
- There is an unexpected obstacle in a way.
- There is another robotic agent requiring sharing the same passage in a same or opposite direction.
- There is an unexpected behaviour of another robotic mobile agent, human operator, or another technology block of production chain.
- There is a “traffic jam” of mobile agents in particular areas so it is necessary to avoid such region.

Such situations will be mostly solved by methods of AI. Since many AI methods requires huge amount of data to train and some of them can provide unpredictable results, it is necessary to make an identical environment compared to a real world, where all the algorithms can be safely trained and tested.

As described in Table 1, we are dealing with mobile robotics agents for industrial transportation. Moreover, the solution will be located at the cloud as well as at the edge. Each agent will be able to solve the transportation task independently (edge computing), but it will be tasked by supervising system taking care about tasks and maintaining changes in the environment reported by agents (cloud computing). The localization of robotic agents will be partly centralized (VICON system) and partly decentralized (robot sensors). The training of the model will also take place in the cloud due to computing power needs, but the trained model will then be employed at the edge to control robotic agents. The employed AI methodology is mostly RL and ROS, Rviz and Unity 3D will be used as a tool to simulate the real-world environment as introduced below.

The modelling of mobile robotic agents can be forked into the 2 views:

- The 3D CAD model of robotic agent for the manufacturing of its hardware.
- The software model of the agent, including its software control and physics modelling for the learning and verification in the digital twin of a real environment.

Both these branches are described in further sections.

5.1.2.1 *CAD modelling of robotic agent's hardware*

Requirements for physical properties result from the requirements of a real industrial plant. The following parameters (Table 3) were selected to obtain good manoeuvrability and sufficient transport capacity.

TABLE 3: PLATFORM PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
Platform type	Omnidirectional
Platform geometry	Round
Platform dimension	Diameter = 0,6 m
Payload capacity	300 kg
Maximum speed	2 m/s (7,2 km/h)

Finally, the chassis with omnidirectional wheels was selected. Instead of the typical three-wheel arrangement, a redundant 4-wheel arrangement has been proposed, mainly to increase robot stability and payload capacity. The resulting design can be seen in Figure 6.

FIGURE 6: OMNIDIRECTIONAL ROBOT DESIGN

Platform description

1st floor

The plan view of the robot shows omnidirectional wheels arrangement that determines the chassis kinematics (Figure 7).

FIGURE 7: 1ST FLOOR PLAN VIEW

The robot wheel consists of 16 segments (Figure 8), each with a free-running hard rubber roller mounted on a separate steel axis (Figure 8).

This slip roller system allows the robot to perform omnidirectional movement and determines the robot kinematics to be described below. The wheel diameter is 306 mm, the roller diameter is 34 mm. Sophisticated mechatronic drive nodes that combine a high-precision cycloid gearbox, a servomotor and feedback sensors are used to drive the robot.

FIGURE 8: ROBOT WHEEL

These drives meet the requirements of limited built-in space as well as optimum price/performance ratio, high tilt, high moment capacity, low weight, compact design, low vibration and high efficiency (Figure 10).

FIGURE 9: WHEEL SEGMENT - EXPLODED VIEW

The last components accommodated on the 1st floor are Li-ion batteries and power electronics.

FIGURE 10: DRIVE NODE

2nd floor

The 2nd floor accommodates mainly sensorics, computing and communication subsystem. The main perception system consists of four overlapping RPLidar (planar TOF 360°) sensors placed above the omnidirectional wheels. The box in the middle of platform covers the computing system – the robot’s brain. The plan view of 2nd floor is in Figure 11.

FIGURE 11: 2ND FLOOR PLAN VIEW

3rd floor

The 3rd floor is intended to be fully user definable. It can accommodate a robotic manipulator, as well as shipping boxes and / or mounting points for material handling and transportation, or any equipment

needed to move around the production area. The plan view of 3rd floor with example of robotic manipulator is in Figure 12.

FIGURE 12: 3RD FLOOR PLAN VIEW

Digital model of robotic agent behaviour

Digitally simulating behaviour of our robotic agent makes development of AI based algorithms used for e.g. autonomous on-board agent navigation more efficient. It is therefore important to have develop a good and easily extendable model of the agent.

The most important part of such model is its kinematics. As was described in previous chapters, the robot was designed to be an omnidirectional four wheeled robot, that uses omnidirectional wheels.

Forward kinematics was very well described in Modern Robotics [30], and their approach to kinematics computation was adopted in development of the robotic agent.

For navigation in the factory where the robot will be placed, it seems to be optimal that the input to the whole kinematics chain are speeds in the world's (factory's) coordinate system (frame).

These speeds then need to be transformed to the robotic agent's frame. Speeds in the robot's frame are then transformed to frames of individual wheels.

First the model of the omnidirectional wheels must be determined. Angular velocity that the wheels spin with are split into two lateral speed components – driving speed and free sliding direction, which combined make up the whole lateral speed of the wheel.

While we cannot control the free sliding speed, we can control the driving speed, that through the free spinning effectively translates to movement of the robotic agent's frame.

Given the wheel parameters and speeds in wheel's frame (obtained using multiple transformations of speed in world's frame), we get the following equation for desired angular speed of the wheel:

$$\omega = \frac{1}{r} (v_{x,wheel} + v_{y,wheel} \tan \gamma) \quad [15].$$

Where γ is the angle between the free sliding speed vector and y-axis of wheel's frame, as can be seen in the Figure 13.

FIGURE 13 DECOMPOSITION OF OMNIDIRECTIONAL WHEEL SPEEDS [30]

With chosen wheels, this angle is zero, therefore we only need to take the speed in x-axis of the wheel's frame into account, reducing the equation to:

$$\omega = \frac{1}{r} v_{x,wheel}.$$

The final forward kinematics with input speeds in world's frame is given by the following equation

$$\vec{\omega} = J \times \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\phi} \\ \dot{v}_x \\ \dot{v}_y \end{bmatrix},$$

where

$$J(i) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{r} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \cos\beta_i & \sin\beta_i \\ -\sin\beta_i & \cos\beta_i \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} -y_i & 1 & 0 \\ x_i & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos\varphi & \sin\varphi \\ 0 & -\sin\varphi & \cos\varphi \end{bmatrix} [15],$$

which represents coordinate system transformations and conversion between linear and angular velocity.

The calculated J matrix is then used to compute the inverse matrix used in inverse kinematics to calculate location differences in the robotic agent simulation. Given the fact, that the matrix dimensions are 4x3, we can remove one of the rows, as there are four actuators for only 3 DOF (degrees of freedom).

The only major dynamics that have an impact on the simulation are ramp generators of the motors. As of now, this is simulated using a linear ramping mechanism, that will be later adjusted using the real ramping mechanism which will be then used in the robotic agent. These dynamics is also the reason why the inverse kinematic of the agent is calculated – the actual speed of the agent might not be the desired speed in moments of motor speed changes.

5.1.2.2 Robotic agent simulation

Simulation of our robotic agent was developed to better visualize and debug algorithms. The current implementation works by calculating motor speeds and position in discrete steps. The whole

simulation was implemented using the Robot Operating System (ROS). ROS is a set of tools and libraries designed to make development, debugging and deployment of robotic algorithms easier. A ROS application consists of many distinct parts called nodes. These nodes can send and receiving messages, that can contain anything from simple number to point clouds and images. There is a special program called ROS Core that is responsible for creating connections between nodes. Splitting programs into nodes allows creation of a distributed system – there is one ROS Core running and many nodes, where each of them can run on different computer/robotic agent as can be seen in the Figure 14.

FIGURE 14 AN EXAMPLE OF A DISTRIBUTED ROS SYSTEM

This will later be used in development of our algorithms, as there will be nodes running on both the robotic agents and on the supervising system. Visualization of data in ROS can be easily done using Rviz – a graphical visualization tool.

FIGURE 15 VISUALIZING THE ROBOT ALONGSIDE WITH AN OBSTACLE AND AVOIDANCE TRAJECTORY

Rviz allows us to implement simple visualization and simulation. In case the need arises for having complex physical simulation Gazebo can be used. It is a complete physical simulation suite for ROS, allowing to simulate for example gravity, friction and inertia.

Our simulated robotic agent was developed as a ROS node responsible for simulating the robotic agent's chassis – more specifically computing its forward and inverse kinematics. It receives messages containing desired speeds of the agent in world's coordinates and sends its current position. The position can then be displayed in Rviz, alongside with for example obstacles, as can be seen in the Figure 15. As of now the simulated digital twin of our robot can be controlled using a simple node that parses gamepad input into the message containing speeds that is sent to the simulating node.

5.1.3 Efficient data streaming to support digital twins (INTRA)

Digital twin refers to a virtual model of potential and actual physical assets (physical twin), processes, people, places, systems, devices, or services. This virtual model can be used for various purposes, including monitoring, diagnostics and prognostics, 3D modelling for the creation of digital companions of the physical objects or creation of embedded systems that allow early fault detection, predictive maintenance or usage monitoring.

A connection between the physical asset and the corresponding virtual model or virtual counterpart (its digital twin) is needed. This connection is established by generating real time data using sensors. The connection of the virtual and physical worlds allows analysis of data and monitoring of systems, to diagnose possible problems before they even occur, preventing downtime and disasters. The same process might result in the development of new opportunities and future planning using simulations. The virtual models update and change as their physical counterparts change. A digital twin should continuously learn and update itself, ingesting various data from multiple sources to represent its near real-time status, working condition or position. This system learns from:

- itself, using sensor data that conveys various aspects of its operating condition,
- historical data from past machine usage to factor into its digital model,
- human experts, such as engineers with deep and relevant industry domain knowledge,
- other similar machines or other similar fleets of machines,
- the larger systems and environment in which it may be a part of.

Apache Kafka platform can be used to implement a successful digital twin infrastructure. Several characteristics offered by Apache Kafka make it an ideal candidate technology for building a reliable and scalable digital twin infrastructure and establish the interconnection between the physical and virtual worlds. These features include:

- Ability to perform **real-time data streaming** and **event-processing**
- **Elasticity and horizontal scalability** - Referring to multiple producers, multiple processors, and multiple consumers.
- **Security features** - Encryption of data streams, authentication and authorization of producers and consumers of the data streams.
- **Reliability** - Kafka is distributed, partitioned, replicated, and fault tolerant, very reliable
- **High fault-tolerance** - Resilient to node failures and support of automatic recovery.
- **Replication** - By using ingest pipelines, Kafka can replicate events allowing parallel processing and experimentation.
- **Connectivity support** - Kafka allows the connectivity for multiple diverse sources and consumers. The different machines and sensors typically provide different types of

interfaces. Confluent Hub offers a huge variety of pre-developed data connectors for data sinks and sources.

- **Long-term storage** - Storage of the data for **re-playing**, reporting, batch analytics, correlations of data from different data sources and other possible use cases that require analysis based on historical data.

The above characteristics and related technologies provide a solid communication backbone for Digital Twins and other components of the system or the Enterprise, which also take in account the needs for real-time communication of increased number of events and the ability to process continuous event streams in order to provide insights and to further understand the related physical systems, enabling their improvement and fine-tuning. Developed simulations can benefit from the publish/subscribe communication pattern to output their state for further processing in a desirable format (json, xml) for other external applications. Similarly, controlling the digital twin is also possible by using the same pattern, with the controlled components interfaces, listening for control messages. The described approach also has the added benefit of supporting the output, communication and control of several Simulation instances (same or different) with relative ease and at scale while allowing the output of components to be used simultaneously by other enterprise applications. Deployments of the described event streaming technologies can be close to the IIoT devices, on premises or in (private or other) cloud allowing for a flexible setup depending on the needs. This in turn allows for a variety of components and systems to interact and effectively results in a more flexible setup which can facilitate efficient interconnections between IIoT, Digital Twins and other applications built around them which aim to support business objectives.

FIGURE 16 DIGITAL TWINS INTERACTIONS WITH COMMUNICATION PLATFORM
(VISUALIZATIONS FROM TUM USED WITH PERMISSION FOR THIS REPORT)

The above figure shows how the streaming platform enables efficient data communication between:

- The real-world assets and their digital twins: The real-world informs the digital twin of real events, as input to simulations or to adapt/retrain the simulation models; the digital twins inform the real world of their results (e.g. on output forecasting or predictive maintenance).

- Within sets of digital twins: Digital twin deployments may involve digital twins for parts (e.g. robotic arms). These digital twins may need to exchange events to implement the digital twin of a composite product (e.g. an assembly line). And where required, the latter digital twins may exchange events to compose the digital twin of a large-scale system (e.g. a factory plant).

With an efficient communication platform in place which enables the straightforward, high-performance, and reliable integration of components, solutions involving collaborative digital twins become easier to realize, investigate and experiment with. The control and subsequent output of Digital Twins developed for individual components can be used in conjunction to discover insights for the entire system which could also be further enriched with data streams from real world components. For example, Digital Twins for machinery (e.g. robotic arms, belts) and for other systems (e.g. power plant) can be used to analyse larger parts of the entire system. This modular approach together with the interconnection of Digital Twins to the extent necessary can be used to discover inter-dependence of components not obvious before, which can highlight further optimization strategies.

5.1.4 Inbound logistic process optimization (ITML)

The focus of this subtopic is the design and implementation of a Material Planning Decision Support System (MPDSS) that operates in an automotive production site in AUDI and aims to optimize the complete inbound logistics process according to the sixth key-target (KT-6) within the framework of the AI4DI project. Towards this direction, ITML's work centres around the employment of advanced data-driven methods to collect and consolidate all relevant information and to use it for the identification of critical parts in the production line.

This information refers to AUDI's internal data and information, AUDI's partner data and information (e.g. OEM's supplier's stock levels), public data information (e.g. weather conditions/forecast, road condition), as well as historical decisions and recommendations in similar situations.

The MPDSS is planned to identify the critical parts that potentially cause a supply bottleneck, thus it (i) focuses on categorizing the parts and (ii) prioritizing them according to the security of supply; (iii) determine level of criticality (critical, very critical, non-critical) and (iv) visualize critical parts and relevant background information. Finally, the MPDSS evaluates all possible measures for securing part supply via assessing all available data and collecting decisions and recommendations, and autonomously prioritises the applicable measures.

This section describes the architectural design of the MPDSS. Based on information provided in Table 1, MDPSS comprises an autonomous system installed at AUDI's production line, where input data do not change within the source systems and there is no manual input or manipulation of data during identification of critical parts and suggestion of countermeasures.

Part autonomy is only delivered during decision on any critical part, as the user can always take the final decision of which countermeasure to apply based on given assessment parameters (e.g. cost, efficiency, CO₂ footprint, etc.). While the data collection (from local and publicly available sites) occurs at the edge, decision support offered by the MPDSS occurs at the cloud side. Training and inference of the ML algorithms happens centrally in the cloud. The AI methodology to follow is supervised training, with the main challenges being the learning prediction.

5.1.4.1 *Requirements - User journeys*

In this section we revisit the user requirements presented in Deliverable D1.11. The user requirements of the Material Planning Decision Support System (MPDSS) will be presented as short user journeys.

Data Collection and Consolidation: The MPDSS should make use of all available information (see Table 4) to identify critical parts, while minimising the necessary actions for the manual collection and consolidation of data.

This is achieved by collecting (i) AUDI's internal data and information; (ii) AUDI's partner data and information; (iii) Public data and information (e.g. weather information, political situations affecting road conditions, etc); and (iv) decisions and recommendations.

Identification of critical parts: The MPDSS should show only those parts that are critical enough to cause a supply bottleneck in the production line.

To achieve this, the system should provide the best possible assessment of criticality by (i) categorising parts and determine critical ones; (ii) prioritising them according to supply capability (how probably it is to obtain this part on time); (iii) visualising critical parts and relevant background information (based on historical data).

Recommendation of measures: The MPDSS should leverage optimisation algorithms to prioritise the different applicable measures for securing part supply and recommend the best-suited measure, taking into consideration certain parameters (e.g. cost, effectiveness, CO₂ footprint).

Autonomous decision making: The MPDSS should autonomously decide which measures are applicable based on given conditions that can be defined by the user either in advance or after the user visualises the suggested countermeasures (partly autonomous decision making). This feature gives a flexible definition of conditions.

Continuous improvement: The user should be able to rate the recommendations given by the MPDSS and this rating should be used to improve the AI routines of the system in the future. This is achieved by comparing user's decision with MPDSS best-fit recommendation (when part autonomous operation).

5.1.4.2 *Software architecture and design*

5.1.4.2.1 Wireframes

To better analyse and document the functionality of the MPDSS, it was considered important to describe the functionality of MPDSS user interface, in the form of wireframes. An application wireframe connects the underlying conceptual structure, or information architecture, to the surface, or visual design of the application.

Wireframes help establish functionality and the relationships between different screen templates of an application (**Figure 17 - Figure 18**).

The produced wireframes purposefully lack typographic style, colour, or graphics, since the focus lies in functionality, behaviour, and priority of content. In other words, they focus on what a screen does, not what it looks like regarding the classification of parts based on the level of criticality and the visualization of analytics of a selected part.

FIGURE 17 (LEFT) CLASSIFICATION OVERVIEW; (RIGHT) DETAILS OF THE SELECTED CRITICAL PART THAT NEED TO BE ADDRESSED

FIGURE 18 (LEFT) ANALYTICS OF A SELECTED PART; (RIGHT) USER MANAGEMENT INTERFACE;

5.1.4.2.2 Data Flow

In this envisioned MPDSS, the data flow is depicted in the following data flow diagram (Figure 19). A streaming platform collects information from AUDI internal data sources (such as warehouse databases) and external data streams (such as weather APIs, traffic condition APIs etc), and all information is fused dynamically in a single dataset. To account for emergency situations such as traffic conditions or natural disasters, this dataset should be updated and queried continuously, so that decision support and alerting is provided in a real-time manner.

FIGURE 19 HIGH LEVEL DATAFLOW DIAGRAM.

5.1.4.2.3 Dataset

The dataset to be collected and consolidated is presented in **Table 4 Dataset for Critical Parts Detection** (with the kind contribution of our partner AUDI). Advanced data analysis will be applied in the below dataset in order to detect critical parts (using a binary classification algorithm that return “1” when a part is critical and “0” when it is not), then assess and recommend countermeasures again

based on calculations from input data, and finally perform decision making and take into consideration the final decision of the user for continuous improvement. There is also consideration into extending the classification of parts into three classes: non-critical, critical and very critical part.

TABLE 4 DATASET FOR CRITICAL PARTS DETECTION

Property	Format
Plant No.	String
Day	DD.MM.YYYY
Supplier No.	Num
Supplier name	String
Supplier location – country	String
Supplier location – city	String
Supplier location – postal code	Num
Supplier distance	Num
Shipping concept	String
Min. coverage	Num
Safety stock advance	Num
Inspection advance	Num
Current stock	Num (,xxx)
End of day stock	Num (,xxx)
Material on transport – day	DD.MM.YYYY
Material on transport – amount	Num (,xxx)
Material in house	Num (,xxx)
Call-off today	Num (,xxx)
Backlog	Num (,xxx)
Demand today	Num (,xxx)
Demand +1 day	Num (,xxx)
Demand +2 days	Num (,xxx)
Demand +3 days	Num (,xxx)
Demand +4 days	Num (,xxx)
Demand +5 days	Num (,xxx)
Material on transport – ETA	DD.MM.YYYY
Supplier replenishment time	Num (,xxx)
Demand -1/.../-5 days	Num (,xxx)
Demand changes today/+1/.../+5 days	Num (,xxx)
Supplier rating	String
Tool broken	Bool
Forwarder rating	String
Line stopper	Bool
Line stock	Num (,xxx)
Weather	String
Heavy traffic	Bool
Season	String
Natural disaster	String
Holidays	Bool
Strike	Bool
Political decisions	String

5.1.4.2.4 MPDSS Architecture

ITML’s Data Fusion Bus (DFB) is well-suited to account for the need of providing real time Machine Learning analytics. Brief reference to DFB and its rationale has been made in Deliverable D1.11, where we stated the requirements for the SC1 use Case. DFB enables organizations in developing, deploying, operating, and managing a big data environment with emphasis on real-time applications. It combines the features and capabilities of several big data applications and utilities within a single platform.

The key capabilities of DFB are:

- Real-time monitoring and event-processing, semantic fusion of events not coinciding in time.
- Data aggregation from heterogeneous data sources and data stores.
- Real time analytics, offering ready to use Machine Learning algorithms for classification, clustering, regression, anomaly detection.
- An extendable and highly customizable Interface REST API (and web app) for configuring analytics, manipulation, and filtering. It also includes functionality for managing the platform.

The technical architecture of MPDSS will be a combination of well-known opensource tools and proprietary modules. ITML will leverage its in-house developed Data Fusion Bus, as depicted in Figure 20.

FIGURE 20. MPDSS ARCHITECTURAL DIAGRAM

The main building blocks of the architecture are:

- **Support for multiple data streams and data stores:** Readily available interfaces are in place that allow for data acquisition for all well-established RDBMSs, data streams (using MQTT), NoSQL databases, shared filesystems (HDFS Hadoop). This functionality is supported by Kafka.
- **Data Fusion Bus,** comprised of the following sub-modules: (i) The Streaming Core of the platform is Apache Kafka. It relies on Kafka ‘s distributed messaging system to provide high fault-tolerance (Resiliency to node failures and support of automatic recovery) and elasticity - high scalability; (ii) Internal Store and Search Engine: When persistence of data within the

platform is required, the Elastic stack (Elasticsearch and Logstash) is utilized. Data may flow either through Kafka connectors (usually in cases of stream data) or may be directly imported to Elasticsearch. Elasticsearch also provides provide high fault-tolerance and scalability; and (iii) Identity management, authentication, authorization and accounting mechanisms that enhance the security of the platform. Moreover, the security mechanism includes dataset encryption and anonymization.

- **DFB Analytics Engine** supports batch processing and stream processing with Apache Spark, Kafka Streams & KSQL, Spark Streaming and python scikit-learn. DFB can be used to perform supervised (classification and regression with algorithms such as RandomForest or neural networks) and unsupervised Machine Learning algorithms (e.g Clustering with Kmeans).
- **DFB Core** is responsible for providing business logic and managing all the data flows. It is a custom REST API (based on Java Spring). It exposes a configurable set of web services for providing Decision Support to external systems and managing/monitoring the whole platform.

A User Interface will be developed (see section 5.1.4.2.1 Wireframes) for presenting the results of the automated process. It will also provide ability for creating custom visualization elements such as graphs, diagrams and tables (provided by Grafana).

5.2 Real time Predictive Maintenance

Predictive maintenance requires to identify faults their consequences as well as providing adequate estimation of the remaining runtime to keep a system operational. In this chapter, we first discuss previous research on predictive maintenance, and afterwards introduce applications of diagnosis as well as an architecture for a system comprising monitoring and diagnostic functionality for providing means for implementing a real time predictive maintenance system.

5.2.1 A survey on predictive maintenance (TUG)

Predictive analytics

Predictive analytics deals with forecasting the future progression of a situation and has a wide range of applications, including weather forecasting [31], epidemiology prediction [32], stock market prediction [33], and *predictive maintenance* [34]. With respect to fault prognosis and maintenance strategy, predictive modelling is essential when implementing predictive maintenance. It aims to improve forecasting accuracy as well as guarantee a robust prediction result, which can save considerable production downtime, labour repair resources and economic loss [35].

Considering information utilization and modelling mechanism, the predictive modelling techniques are categorized into three groups [36]:

1. *Physics-based*
2. *Data-driven*
3. *Model-based*

1. The physics-based approach typically describes the physical behaviours of a system using the *first principle as a series of ordinary or partial differential equations* according to the law of physics [37].

For example, one typical application to crack growth rate is governed by a power law, such as Paris' law [38]. However, the construction of a physics model is usually *difficult since it requires detailed and complete knowledge of a complex system*. On the other hand, it *lacks extensive failure samples* to determine the model parameters in practice.

2. *The data driven approach* does not rely on physical knowledge, and it constructs a model representing the underlying relationship of a system based on data mining techniques. The data driven approach could be grouped into two categories including:

- *Statistical and*
- *Artificial-intelligence-based models.*

The *typical statistical models* include the *autoregressive model* and its variations, linear regression, wiener process, and Gamma process, etc.

Artificial-intelligence-based models include *artificial neural network, clustering classification, extreme learning machine, fuzzy logic, and deep learning models.*

However, the performance of the data driven model is sensitive to the size and quality of the collected dataset and the constructed model is application specific.

3. In comparison, the *model-based approach* [39] takes advantage of established physical knowledge and collected data to enhance the prediction performance. It typically involves two steps including *model construction* and *model updating* [40]. First, analytical models are built based on the physical or empirical model representing the situation evolution in a quantitative manner. These models are then updated with newly acquired information to predict the future progression of the situation based on *Bayesian inference*. Comparing with the data driven approach, the model-based approach *requires less historical data to construct the models*. The predicted value is associated with a confidence level, resulting from the uncertainty involved in the prediction process [41].

TABLE 5 COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT PREDICTIVE MODELING TECHNIQUES REGARDING DEFECT PROGNOSIS

Category	Applicable Domain	Typical Models
Physics based approach	Devices of the same type, require abundant failure samples	Paris law, Taylor model
Data driven approach	Devices of the same type, require abundant degradation samples	Neural network, SVM, ELM, RVM, SOM, HMM
Model based approach	Single device, require single degradation samples	AR model, ARMA, linear regression
	Single device, require single degradation samples	Kalman Filter, Particle filter

One major factor that needs to be considered for selecting an appropriate prognostic method is the *required information input and assumptions* for prognostic models. In the case of limited degradation data available, the model-based approach is appropriate. Based on the relevant physical mechanisms, *state evolution models and measurement models* that relate the sensor output to the underlying machine states are established. Subsequently, the machine state can be inferred given new measurements, by means of *estimating the posterior probability density function (PDF)*.

II. Predictive Maintenance: Motivation, Concept, Variants and Standards

According to [42], maintenance costs can represent up to 60 percent of the total production costs, hence optimizing equipment utilization is of major importance.

In order to understand predictive maintenance, we have to state first the traditional maintenance techniques. Industrial and process plants typically employ two types of maintenance management: *failure-driven* and *time-based maintenance*.

Failure-driven maintenance, a.k.a. run-to-failure maintenance, is a reactive maintenance approach which is carried out only after the occurrence of a malfunction, or breakdown of equipment [43].

Time-based maintenance, a.k.a. periodic preventive maintenance or just preventive maintenance, is based on either mean time between functional failures (MTBF) or machine usage [44].

Predictive maintenance, a.k.a. condition-based predictive maintenance (CBPdM or CBM or PdM), is a condition-driven preventive maintenance program. Instead of running a part until failure, like reactive maintenance, or replacing a good part which may have life left, like preventive maintenance, predictive maintenance uses direct monitoring of the mechanical condition, system efficiency, and other indicators or algorithms to determine the actual mean-time-to-failure or loss of efficiency for each machine-train and system in the plant. At best, traditional time-driven methods provide a guideline to "normal" machine-train life spans.

Due to the increasing technical possibilities to monitor, store, and analyse conditions, predictive maintenance strategies are gaining popularity. Among the benefits of predictive maintenance, we can mention: fewer equipment downtime and fewer urgent work-order requests, enhanced asset performance, considerably improved asset reliability, overall enrichment of the business performance, better budget planning.

The relative benefit of predictive maintenance, however, strongly depends on the behaviour of the deterioration process and the severity of failures. Furthermore, it is affected by various practical factors that are often present in practice, required planning time, imperfect condition monitoring, and variation in the deterioration level at which failure occurs. Hence predictive maintenance should only be applied if this relative benefit outweighs the efforts and costs during the entire life cycle that are required to apply this type of maintenance [45, 46, 47]. The requisites to switch from time-based to condition-based maintenance include condition monitoring equipment and software to store, analyse, and initiate maintenance actions [48].

Considering the definition from [49], a predictive maintenance (PdM) program consists basically of three key steps:

- (1) *Data acquisition* (information collecting), to obtain data relevant to system health,
- (2) *Data processing* (information handling), to handle and analyse the data or signals collected in step (1),
- (3) *Maintenance decision-making*, to recommend efficient maintenance policies.

Data acquisition is the process of collecting and storing information from targeted physical assets for the purpose of PdM. Data collected in a PdM program can be categorised into two main types: the so-called event data and condition monitoring data. Event data include the information on what happened (e.g., breakdown, overhaul, etc., and what the causes were) and/or what was done (e.g., minor repair, preventive maintenance, oil change, etc.) to the targeted physical asset. Condition monitoring data are the measurements related to the health condition/state of the physical asset. Condition monitoring data are very versatile. As mentioned in [49], it can be vibration data, acoustic data, oil analysis data, pressure, temperature, moisture, humidity, weather or environment data, etc. The authors of [49] take three types of data into consideration:

- Value type: Data collected at a specific point in time for a condition monitoring variable are a single value. For example, oil analysis data, temperature, pressure and humidity are all value type data.
- Waveform type: Data collected at a specific point in time for a condition monitoring variable are a time series, which is often called time waveform. For example, vibration data and acoustic data are waveform type.

- Multidimensional type: Data collected at a specific point in time for a condition monitoring variable are multidimensional. The most common multidimensional data are image data such as infrared thermographs, X-ray images, visual images, etc.

Various sensors, such as micro-sensors, ultrasonic sensors, acoustic emission sensors, etc., have been designed to collect different types of data. For more details, we refer the interested reader to paper [49].

Further on, in data processing, the first step is data cleaning. This is an important step since data, especially event data, which is usually entered manually, always contains errors. Data cleaning ensures, or at least increases the chance, that error-free data are used for further analysis and modelling. For condition monitoring data, data errors may be caused by sensor faults. In this case, sensor fault isolation is the right way to go. In general, however, there is no simple way to clean data. Sometimes it requires manual examination of data. Graphical tools are very helpful to finding and removing data errors [49].

The next step of data processing is data analysis. A variety of models, algorithms and tools are available in the literature to analyse data for better understanding and interpretation of data. The models, algorithms and tools used for data analysis depend mainly on the types of data collected. For more details, we refer the reader to paper [49].

As depicted in [49], the last step of a PdM program is maintenance decision-making. Techniques for maintenance decision support in a PdM program can be divided into two main categories [49]: *diagnostics and prognostics*. Fault diagnostics focuses on detection, isolation and identification of faults when they occur. Prognostics, however, attempts to predict faults or failures before they occur. Obviously, prognostics is superior to diagnostics in the sense that prognostics can prevent faults or failures, still prognostics cannot completely replace diagnostics since in practice there are always some faults and failures which are not predictable. Besides, prognostics, like any other prediction techniques, cannot be 100% sure to predict faults and failures. In the case of unsuccessful prediction, diagnostics can be a complementary tool for providing maintenance decision support. In addition, diagnostic is also helpful to improving prognostics in the way that diagnostic information can be useful for preparing more accurate event data and hence building better PdM model for prognostics. Furthermore, diagnostic information can be used as useful feedback information for system redesign. Jardine [50] reviewed and compared several commonly used PdM decision strategies such as trend analysis that is rooted in statistical process control (SPC), expert systems (ESs), and neural networks. Wang and Sharp [51] discussed decision aspect of PdM and reviewed the recent development in modelling PdM decision support.

In [49], the authors group the techniques applied to machine diagnosis into: *statistical approaches, AI approaches and other methods including model-based approaches*. In Section V, we will further focus on the model-based approaches.

Compared to diagnostics, the literature of prognostics is much smaller. There are two main prediction types in machine prognostics. The most obvious and widely used prognostics is to predict how much time is left before a failure occurs given the current machine condition and past operation profile. The time left before observing a failure is usually called *remaining useful life (RUL)*. The second type of prognostics is to predict the chance that a machine operates without a fault or a failure up to some future time (e.g., next inspection interval) given the current machine condition and past operation

profile. Most of the papers in the literature of machine prognostics discuss only the first type of prognostics, namely RUL estimation. For more information, we refer the reader to paper [49].

FIGURE 21 FOUR LEVELS OF MATURITY IN PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE [52]

Over the past 30 years, predictive maintenance has been evolving from predicting failures based on periodic visual inspections to continuous real-time monitoring of assets and external data with alerts based on statistical techniques such as regression analysis for at least one important asset. Furthermore, the advent of Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) technology has significantly optimized the industrial operations management by connecting industrial assets with information systems and, hence, with business processes.

Predictive Maintenance 4.0 (PdM 4.0) or Maintenance 4.0, is among the major focus points of IIoT. In [52] the authors identify four levels of maturity in predictive maintenance, depicted in Figure 21.

Many companies are combining the capabilities of IIoT and Big Data to predict equipment malfunctions. The accuracy of forecast is further getting more precise with improved AI techniques and machine learning tools. As depicted in [53], Maintenance 4.0 forms a subset of smart manufacturing systems which are autonomous in their operation, capable of predicting failures and triggering maintenance activities. These systems consist of smart equipment in form of embedded or cyber-physical systems forming the digital twin of physical assets. To achieve near zero defects, near zero down time and automated decision making based on condition monitoring, *world class diagnostics and prognostics* need to be implemented [54]. According to [53], the most advanced form

of maintenance is *prescriptive maintenance* which builds on PdM as it provides further guidance on the maintenance task as well as provide diagnostics [55].

Prescriptive maintenance strategies extensively use advanced data processing and visualization techniques such as graph analysis, simulations, neural networks, complex event processing, heuristics and machine learning. These tools provide the capability to calculate the timing and effect of failure, thus, determining the priority and urgency of the maintenance activity.

In order to get the most out of PdM 4.0., the authors of [52] propose the following 6 steps schema:

1. Asset value ranking & feasibility study

Identify assets for which implementing PdM 4.0 is worthwhile and feasible to increase asset reliability. Only highly critical and perhaps moderately-critical assets will justify the required investments. In addition, only assets for which the required data can be obtained will be suitable candidates.

2. Reliability modelling

Use *root cause analysis (RCA)* and *failure mode and effects analysis (FMEA)* per asset type to point you in the right direction. Which data is needed to monitor root causes and failure modes? Which sensory data and external data sets are needed for this? How are the various root causes and failure modes interrelated? This is the step where reliability engineers and data scientists should interact and complement each other.

3. PdM 4.0 algorithm design

Choosing an algorithm is the most important factor in determining the quality of your predictions. It may be relatively straightforward to design an effective algorithm if you have already built an appropriate model for asset reliability, as mentioned in the previous step. Several data scientists may also be needed to construct a self-learning algorithm capable of finding meaningful insights in pools of data.

4. Real-time performance monitoring

The algorithm processes data from various sources - sensors embedded in the asset, the asset's maintenance and failure history or third-party providers of environmental data - to monitor and visualize the performance of your assets in real-time.

5. Failure prediction

The algorithm will start to predict future failures. Acting on these predictions - by actually shutting down machines or taking perfectly operational trains out of circulation - may initially require a big leap of faith, especially if management and maintenance staff have little experience or affinity with data analytics. If this is the case, PdM 4.0 could run parallel with existing maintenance procedures without taking maintenance actions based on its predictions.

6. Preventive task prescription

At the highest level of PdM 4.0, the algorithm not only predicts when a failure is likely to occur, but it also draws from a library of standard maintenance tasks to prescribe the best action for avoiding such a failure. It may even execute such tasks, for example, by automatically issuing the corresponding work order.

As standards are actually the basis for introducing new technologies and innovations, [53] describes the existing open standards related to condition-based maintenance (see Table 6 from [53]) and how the research/industrial community has benefitted from them.

TABLE 6 INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS RELATED TO CBM [53]

Standards	Description
IEEE 1451	Smart transducer interface for sensors and actuators
IEEE 1232	Artificial Intelligence Exchange and Service Tie to All Test Environment
ISO 13372	Condition monitoring and diagnostics of machines - Vocabulary
ISO 13373-1	Condition monitoring and diagnostics of machines - Vibration condition monitoring - Part 1. General procedures
ISO 13373-2	Condition monitoring and diagnostics of machines - Vibration condition monitoring - Part 2. Processing, analysis and presentation of vibration data
ISO 13374	MIMOSA OSA-CBM formats and methods for communicating, presenting and displaying relevant information and data
ISO 13380	Condition monitoring and diagnostics of machines - General guidelines on using performance parameters
ISO 13381-1	Condition monitoring and diagnostics of machines - Prognostics, general guidelines
ISO 14224	Petroleum, petrochemical and natural gas industries - collection and exchange of reliability and maintenance data for equipment
ISO 17359	Condition monitoring and diagnostics of machines - General guidelines
ISO 18435	MIMOSA OSA-EAI diagnostic and maintenance applications integration
ISO 55000	Asset management

OSA-PdM and OSA-EAI standards

The Open System Architecture for Condition-Based Maintenance (OSA-PdM) specification is an open-standards-based architecture which acts as a reference point for implementing condition-based maintenance systems. It was developed in 2001 by an industry led team partially funded by the US Navy through the DUST program [56]. OSA-PdM is a robust non-proprietary standard which added details of data structures and interface methods for implementing the six blocks of functionality in a condition monitoring system defined by the ISO-13374 standard (Condition Monitoring and Diagnostics of Machines). OSA-PdM has become the de-facto standard for PdM, encompassing the complete range of functions from data collection through to the recommendation of specific maintenance actions.

The Open Systems Architecture for Enterprise Application Integration (OSA-EAI) is another standard developed and managed by MIMOSA which defines data structures for storing and progressing information about all characteristics of equipment into enterprise applications.

It focuses on information integration of asset life-cycle management (ALM) applications using a common standardized maintenance database, which is one level above the condition monitoring (CM) systems. OSA-PdM data can be directly mapped into any OSA-EAI compliant relational database maintenance systems with ease, allowing better integration of CM and ALM systems. Examples of OSA-EAI compliant commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) software are Emerson Process Management RBMWare, Rockwell Emonitor Odyssey and IBM Maximo Oil and Gas.

III. Time-based Maintenance vs. Condition-based Maintenance. Comparative studies

McKone and Weiss [57] consider the integration of condition-based maintenance with traditional periodic preventive maintenance. The available condition information is limited to a signal of a potential failure that might be received before the actual failure. The probability that this signal is received depends on the prediction accuracy, and the time between the signal and the failure depends on the prediction precision. Hence, the performance of the condition-based maintenance strategy depends on the prediction accuracy and precision.

In some situations, periodic preventive maintenance or a combination of condition-based and periodic preventive maintenance is preferred. Paté-Cornell et al. [58] use a Markov chain with four states to model the deterioration process of a production system. Time-based maintenance and three types of

condition-based maintenance are considered. The latter are based on inspections of the product, signals of the machine, and signals provided using the product.

Zhang et al. [59] develop an adaptive discrete-state model based on Bayesian Belief Network theory. Both Paté-Cornell et al. [58] and Zhang et al. [59] consider a single illustrative example, and no attempt is made to generalize the results.

Other studies consider deterioration processes with a continuous state space. Pandey et al. [60] use gamma deterioration processes and linear deterioration processes with a random (but fixed) rate. Xiang et al. [61] also adopt linear processes, but consider a rate that depends on the environment in which the system operates. This environment is represented by a continuous-time Markov chain with three states.

Crowder and Lawless [62] consider gamma and Wiener processes, and Zio and Compare [63] adopt the randomized Paris-Erdogan fatigue crack growth model.

For the main part of their analysis, Pandey et al. [60] consider the threshold deterioration level that triggers preventive maintenance as fixed. Only a limited investigation also includes the threshold deterioration level as a decision variable. Condition-based maintenance turns out to be preferred over time-based maintenance only if the coefficient of variation of the lifetime exceeds a certain level.

Crowder and Lawless [62] and Zio and Compare [63] compare the optimal condition-based maintenance policy with the optimal time-based maintenance policy, but they only do so for a single specification of the parameters. In both studies, the performance of condition-based maintenance turns out to be much better than that of time-based maintenance for the considered parameter settings, but general insights are lacking.

Xiang et al. [61] include randomness in the deterioration level at which failure occurs, and show that there is potential cost saving through implementing a condition-based maintenance policy as opposed to time-based maintenance. No insights are presented on the effect of changes in the other model parameters on these cost savings.

More sophisticated models are considered by Huynh et al. [64] and by Bouvard et al. [65]. The former combine failures due to deterioration with failures due to shock events. Because failures are not self-announcing but should be identified by inspections, a cost is introduced for system inactivity. A condition-based strategy with periodic inspections is compared with a purely time-based block replacement strategy.

A clear effect of the type of condition deterioration is lacking, as only two deterioration processes are considered (high and low variance).

The influence of the values of the cost parameters is studied in more detail and the relative benefit of the condition-based strategy turns out to increase in the preventive replacement cost. Bouvard et al. [65] develop a maintenance model that dynamically optimizes the maintenance decisions for a multi-component system at each periodic inspection time. Maintenance actions are grouped to reduce maintenance costs. A system with three components is considered as an example and it is shown that the use of condition information leads to lower costs compared with the case that this information is not used. Cost savings are most significant for short times between inspections and moderate variances of the underlying gamma processes that are used to model deterioration of the components.

IV. Factors influencing the benefits of Condition-based Maintenance [66]

Required planning time

A certain planning time (sometimes also called *lead time* or *delay time*) is required between initiating and performing a maintenance action. Many authors consider a planning time to perform maintenance in combination with a continuously monitored unit that deteriorates according to a Gamma stochastic process. They all assume that maintenance is scheduled if the level of deterioration exceeds a certain alarm level.

In Bérenguer et al. [67], the maintenance policy is fully determined by an alarm threshold \bar{A} , where \bar{A} is lower than the failure level \bar{L} . When the considered aging variable reaches the failure level, a breakdown occurs. Moreover, the continuous monitoring is assumed to be “perfect” i.e., the condition of the system is known with no error or uncertainty at any time. When the aging variable exceeds \bar{A} , a maintenance operation is planned. This operation occurs after a delay time τ and its duration depends on the deterioration state of the system at the beginning of the maintenance action. Since the system still deteriorates during the delay time τ , a breakdown can occur between the alarm time and the onset of the maintenance action. Obviously, the choice of the alarm threshold \bar{A} will influence the performance of the maintenance policy. If the threshold \bar{A} is close to \bar{L} , the probability of breakdown is great. If the threshold \bar{A} is low, the probability of breakdown is small, but unnecessary maintenance operations are done on a system with a long potential residual life. Therefore, the authors compute the asymptotic unavailability of the maintained system and they find the preventive maintenance policy which minimizes this unavailability.

Bouvard et al. [65] study a multi-components system with grouped maintenance actions to reduce maintenance costs. The proposed maintenance model includes a certain minimal time required to prepare and organize maintenance. It is supposed that the time between the current date and the next maintenance stop is greater than this minimal planning time.

Van Oosterom et al. [68] define the delay time as the time elapsed from the occurrence of a defect up until failure. Hence a delay time model (DTM) is developed to determine the optimal policy for a single-component system under a new assumption: postponed replacement.

Instead of immediate replacement, enforced as soon as a defect is detected, they allow replacement to be postponed for an additional time period. This results in a better utilization of the system’s useful life and in a reduced replacement cost by providing sufficient time window to prepare maintenance resources.

Imperfect condition monitoring

Condition information may contain noise due to errors in measurement and interpretation, and due to the limited accuracy of the measuring instruments. Typical condition monitoring techniques like vibration and oil debris monitoring, which are widely applied in industry, generally result in such inaccuracies. These techniques can therefore be considered as imperfect [69]. Still when considering the crack growth of a mechanical component subject to fatigue degradation, observations of the crack depth at inspections are just estimations of the true values [63].

According to [36], the simplest models that include imperfect condition monitoring contain two or three deterioration states, and inspections reveal the true system state with a given probability.

Ghasemi et al. [70] model the deterioration state using a discrete time Markov process, Makis and Jiang [71] and Moghaddass and Zuo [72] use a continuous time Markov process. They all relate the unobservable system state to the observed system state through an observation probability matrix. Le and Tan [73] also use a continuous time Markov process and combine imperfect continuous monitoring with perfect inspections. MacPherson and Glazebrook [74] consider continuously monitored two-phase systems. Transitions from the fault free to the worn state might not be observed, and indications of transitions might also be false.

In many cases, the imperfect condition information has been combined with deterioration processes, which were modelled as continuous stochastic processes. Kallen and Van Noortwijk [75] use a gamma deterioration process, Peng and Tseng [76] a linear trend with random coefficient plus a Brownian motion as a second random effect, Ye et al. [77] a Wiener process with positive drift, and Zio and Compare [63] a Randomized Paris-Erdogan fatigue crack growth model. In all these cases, inspections have to be performed in order to obtain condition information and the measurement error is modelled by independent normal distributions.

Xiang et al. [61] define a model in which the rate of deterioration depends on the environment, and the measurement error is modelled by a normal random variable. However, the authors assume that this error is constant over time, which may often be unrealistic.

Their analysis indicates that even small levels of measurement errors can significantly affect the benefit of condition-based maintenance over time-based maintenance.

The study of Zio and Compare [63] indicates that for large measurement errors the performance of condition-based maintenance gets worse if the number of inspections increases.

All measurement errors are modelled by independent normal distributions and preventive maintenance is performed when a single observed deterioration level exceeds a safety threshold. However, if the number of inspections is large, it becomes likely that one of the observed deterioration levels exceeds the safety threshold while the real deterioration level is still low.

This can be avoided by using a decision rule for initiating preventive maintenance that does not only take the most recent condition measurement into account. An alternative is to model the noise by a Brownian motion, as for example done by Elwany et al. [78] and Li and Ryan [79].

Uncertainty in the deterioration level at which failure occurs

According to Jiang [80], uncertainty in the failure level is especially relevant if the deterioration process is represented by several condition variables that are combined into a composite condition variable. Abdel-Hameed [81], Van Horenbeek and Pintelon [82], Xiang et al. [61] model the deterioration level at which failure occurs as a random variable. Some of them assume a specific distribution (normal, exponential, Weibull, gamma, and lognormal distribution are used). Jiang [80] makes this random variable time-dependent.

Other models where failure does not occur at a fixed level of deterioration are those in which the failure rate depends on condition variables. Kong and Park [82] consider a failure rate that depends on a single condition variable.

Examples of models that allow the failure rate to depend on multiple condition variables are the proportional hazards model (PHM) and the accelerating failure time (AFT) model.

V. Model based Diagnosis and Predictive Maintenance

In this section, we focus on maintenance decision-making techniques, and particularly on model-based approaches.

The model-based approaches utilise physics specific, explicit mathematical model of the monitored machine. Based on this explicit model, residual generation methods such as Kalman filter, parameter estimation and parity relations are used to obtain signals, called residuals, which is indicative of fault presence in the machine. Finally, the residuals are evaluated to arrive at fault detection, isolation and identification. According to [49], *model-based approaches can be more effective than other model-free approaches if a correct and accurate model is built*. However, explicit mathematical modelling may not be feasible for complex systems since it would be very difficult or even impossible to build mathematical models for such systems. Various model-based diagnostic approaches have been applied to fault diagnosis of a variety of mechanical systems such as gearboxes [83, 84], bearings [85, 86, 87], rotors [88, 89] and cutting tools [90].

[49] also mentions here Bartelmus [90, 91], who used mathematical modelling and computer simulation to aid signal processing and interpretation. Hansen et al. [92] proposed an approach to more robust diagnosis based on the fusion of sensor-based and model-based information. Vania and Pennacchi [93] developed some methods to measure the accuracy of the results obtained with model-based techniques aimed to identify faults in rotating machines.

The information provided by these methods was shown to be very helpful to having more precise fault identification along with evaluating the confidence of a diagnostic decision.

Two practical successful applications of maintenance programs using model-based approaches are the TIGER system described in [94] and the integrated framework for on-board fault diagnosis and failure prognosis of a helicopter transmission component introduced in [95].

Back in 1992, there was already a major move towards condition-based maintenance and condition monitoring of gas turbines, the goal being to monitor the turbine on a regular basis in order to establish when maintenance actions need to be performed based on the condition of the turbine rather than a fixed number of operating hours. The developed TIGER system [96] integrates several artificial intelligence technologies, including qualitative model-based reasoning to perform condition monitoring of gas turbines.

The TIGER diagnostic mechanism uses 3 independent tools and a fault manager which is used to coordinate the conclusions of these tools. It should be noted that each tool runs independently, i.e., the tools can all work in parallel, each examining different aspects of the turbine for an early detection of problems. This also means that for each application, the appropriate subset of these tools can be selected. The tools are as follows:

- KHEOPS [97] is a high-speed rule-based system. It is used to express diagnostic rules in a classic rule-based formalism. It also allows the user to set oriented pre-alarm limits for each parameter.
- IxTeT [96] is used to either describe the normal causal reaction or look for specific patterns resulting from known faults.
- CA-EN [98] is a model-based supervision system devoted to complex dynamic systems. CA-EN's representation formalism allows one to combine empirical causal knowledge and first

principles of the domain. CA-EN has two processing modules: a simulation module, which produces the explicit behaviour of the physical system in terms of the values of the internal variables across time according to the behaviour of the exogenous variables, and a diagnosis module, which accounts for fault detection and isolation of faulty components.

In CA-EN, the authors deal with time explicitly, abstracting it to a logical clock-based sampled time. Among other things, having a linear temporal scale allows to easily evaluate state durations and event dates and to be synchronous with the observations coming in real time from the physical system [94]. The CA-EN prediction algorithm performs a simulation, i.e. prediction across time. The input data are the causal model - including initial conditions - and the evolution of the measured variables of the causal graph over time. The output of the system is the behaviour of each process variable which is displayed as the process runs [94]. Further on, The CA-EN diagnosis algorithm includes two procedures: fault detection which is based on the results of the prediction mechanism, and conflict and diagnosis generation which follow Reiter's diagnosis methodology [39].

[95] describes an integrated framework for on-board fault diagnosis and failure prognosis of a helicopter transmission component - the planetary gear carrier plate of the main rotor transmission.

The framework can detect with minimum false alarms incipient failure of the carrier plate and predict its time to failure. The enabling technologies, illustrated in Figure 22 Diagnosis and prognosis framework Figure 22, include statistical tools for sensor data validation, de-noising of data using blind deconvolution, model-based techniques for extracting an optimum condition-indicator vector, and a combination of measurements and Bayesian estimation algorithms to detect and identify a fault and predict RUL with specified confidence.

FIGURE 22 DIAGNOSIS AND PROGNOSIS FRAMEWORK [95]

First, a suite of algorithms is used to distinguish sensor faults from symptoms of mechanical component faults (i.e., valid sensor data) in order to reduce false alarms. Afterwards a de-noising algorithm is applied to the vibration signals collected from the gearbox. The de-noising scheme makes use of the frequency-domain characterizations of the vibration signals offered by the diagnostic vibration model as a noiseless reference.

The diagnostic vibration model simulates changes in vibration data caused by the presence of the crack in the carrier plate. Further on the prognostic model provides a deterministic estimate of the crack-length progression curve. This estimate is dependent upon the initial crack length, which is determined by the diagnosis task. Bayesian considerations are used to manage and interpret the inherent uncertainty in the initial crack length. The crack progression curve is used to estimate the number of

load cycles remaining before *the critical crack length* is reached, as illustrated by the authors in Figure 23.

FIGURE 23 MODEL-BASED PROGNOSIS ARCHITECTURE [95]

5.2.2 AI based diagnostic and control of electrical drives (BUT)

This subtopic deals with the implementation of AI techniques in electrical drives, namely in the motor and inverter. The idea is to use the AI methods for the diagnosis of electric drives faults and for the controller optimization to operate with maximum efficiency.

As it can be seen in Table 1, this subtopic addressed by BUT is on the subsystem level as the electric drives are just parts of larger system like machines, conveyors, valves, cars and others. The goal is to operate mainly on the edge in a real-time. The diagnostic results, or at least pre-processed data reduced in size will be sent to the cloud. The training will be executed on the cloud. It will use the data from real experiments (where it is possible) but mainly from the appropriate models simulating individual drive faults. Utilization of models will simplify the marking of the data because the position and type of the fault will be known. The amount of experiments can be huge without destroying drives. MATLAB Simulink will be used to generate data sets. Therefore, we plan to use supervised learning in combination with deep learning for the perception and reasoning. To reduce the training time of the neural network, some pre-trained network will be selected, like GoogLeNet. GoogLeNet is the winner of ImageNet Large Scale Visual Recognition Competition (ILSVRC) organized during ECCV 2014. The Deep learning toolbox available in MATLAB will be used for the ANN training.

The efficiency maximization will be also realized on the edge. The reinforced learning will be used to cope with different motor operating conditions.

In both cases we plan to use AURIX microcontroller from Infineon for the purpose of control and data measurement. Data will be processed in Nvidia Jetson Nano/Xavier graphical chip which is designed for AI in embedded applications.

5.2.2.1 Modelling

The development of appropriate electrical drive model in classical Simulink is impossible because the causality is fixed there. But some motor/inverter faults like fallen wire, damaged winding, open circuit in inverter power transistor cause the change of causality. Therefore, the motor model in Simscape tool was taken from previous project and conditioned for the purpose of generating data sets for neural network learning.

The parameters were taken from existing small motor which enables controlled fault injection in motor windings. This motor will serve as a bridge between pure simulation and real experimental results. The possible faults are limited on this experimental setup while the simulation will enable to generate rich data sets. The motor model must rely on the knowledge of winding geometry inside of the motor. It leads to more complicated model comparing to one which is normally used for motor control design.

FIGURE 24 REAL MOTOR WITH FAULT INJECTION CAPABILITIES CONNECTED TO DYNAMOMETER TEST BENCH

To increase the credibility of the achieved results, the motor with higher power is in the process of manufacturing by the external supplier.

5.2.2.2 Preparation of AI hardware setup

AURIX Application Kit with the microcontroller AURIX TCxxx was connected with Nvidia Jetson Nano evaluation board using SPI connection and using Ethernet 100 Mbit connection.

The realized interconnection profits from the achievable safety level of the microcontroller which is especially designed to operate up to ASIL D automotive applications and from Nvidia platform which is capable to accommodate trained neural network.

FIGURE 25 CONTROLLER UNIT BLOCK DIAGRAM

The SPI connection is running properly up to 15 Mbit in the laboratory conditions. The conditioned software is running on both platforms in bidirectional mode. Ethernet connection also works in both directions. It enables to send data for fast processing in the Nvidia platform send back the status result (see Figure 25). Some motor or inverter faults require to increase sampling rate of current measurement above PWM frequency. The AURIX microcontroller driver is being prepared which enables to measure the currents with sampling period equal to 2 us (corresponds to 500 kHz sampling frequency). The real limit of the AD converter is around 1.2 us. The DMA transfer is initiated after each conversion to put the measurement in the buffer for sending using above mentioned channels.

5.2.2.3 Simulation results

The preliminary simulation results show the detection of inter-turn short circuit fault in Permanent Magnet Synchronous (PMS) motors which are controlled using field-oriented control algorithm by using Artificial Neural Network. The utilization of the GoogLeNet drastically reduces the training time. It is pre-trained convolutional neural network with 22 build in layers. It requires images as inputs. The measured 1D data of phase voltages and currents (see Figure 26) were filtered and normalized so as to lose the dependency on rotational speed.

FIGURE 26 PHASE VOLTAGES AND CURRENTS FOR HEALTHY MOTOR (ON THE RIGHT) AND THE INFLUENCE OF INTER-TURN SHORT CIRCUIT (ON THE LEFT)

With the normalization we mean oversampling or under sampling so as to have equal number of periods in the signal for further processing.

The fault is nicely visible on an envelope of phase currents and voltages. The envelope signal is then transformed into 2D data (images) as can be seen in following figures. The wavelet transformation was used for this task.

Computed scalograms for healthy and unhealthy motor are shown in Figure 27 and Figure 28. Unhealthy motor has short circuited (SC) 10 turns of winding out of 75. The task is complicated with the fact that scalograms depend not only on the level of the fault but also on the motor speed and motor load. Each image contains the information in RGB components.

Red colour is used for the speed, green colour is used for the voltage envelope and blue colour is used for current envelope. The neural network is actually trained using 40 k of images.

The goal is not only to say that the fault appeared but also to estimate the level of the interturn short circuit impact on the future motor behaviour. Deep Learning Toolbox from MATLAB was used to learn neural network using back-propagation algorithm.

FIGURE 27 LOAD FREE PMS MOTOR

FIGURE 28 PMS MOTOR LOADED WITH 1 NM

It is possible to see the difference in the figures representing healthy and faulty motor behaviour. The neural network enables to distinguish between them. The success ratio is around 99 %. It also enables to estimate the number of short-circuited coil turns. The situation is slightly worse in case of data provided from the real motor. The presence of noise in some cases leads to faulty decision about the depth of the problem. Further research is needed and will be realized in course of WP4.

5.2.3 An architecture for model-based predictive maintenance (TUG)

Based on the survey we further investigated on an implementation architecture for real-time predictive maintenance focusing on available models that can be integrated into an existing system without compromising the original system’s behaviour.

To assure the least influence between existing systems and a predictive maintenance system, we assume that both are running on different platforms requiring only little interactions.

Necessary interactions are for obtaining measurements and the internal state of the original system. These observations have to be provided to a monitoring unit, which is responsible for storing this information and providing it to other parts of the predictive maintenance system.

FIGURE 29 AN ARCHITECTURE COMBINING DIAGNOSTICS, MONITORING, AND DIGITAL TWINS FOR REAL TIME PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE

In Figure 29, we give an overview of the suggested solution where we see on the left the original system under operation interacting with its environment and coupled with the monitoring unit. The monitoring unit itself is coupled with a digital twin, i.e., digital replica of the system under operation, that is able to perform a similar behaviour than the system under operation itself.

Hence, we are able to compare the behaviour suggested by the digital twin with the real behaviour of the system under operation. In case of deviations, we feed all the information into a failure handling unit providing diagnostic capabilities.

In case of predictive maintenance these capabilities include identifying the root causes of the failures, as well as their consequences on the operation. This includes as well as giving estimates on remaining

runtime and necessary replacements of units and modules in the system under operation. Moreover, we may also consider to bring the system under operation into a state so that a fault will not lead to situations where safety requirements cannot be assured anymore.

Hence, the system under operation has to provide an interface for a monitoring device, as well as an interface allowing to feedback diagnostic information for preventing unwanted consequences of faults. It is worth noting that the provided predictive maintenance architecture is general and does not rely on any diagnosis method. However, within AI4DI we want to further investigate on the use of model-based diagnosis for predictive maintenance combining models of the correct behaviour with fault models. In addition, we plan to add methods allowing for giving estimations of the remaining time of operation and to simulate the overall systems comprising the system under operation and as well as the model-based predictive maintenance framework.

FIGURE 30 SIMULATION ENVIRONMENT USED FOR TESTING THE MODEL-BASED PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE FRAMEWORK.

For this purpose, we suggest using models written in the simulation language Modelica for both the system under operation and as well as the digital twin. Modelica is a general modelling language implementing the object-oriented programming paradigm. The overall test system to be carried out at TUG is depicted in Figure 30. To be more realistic, we assume that the Modelica model representing the system under operation can only be observed at specific time points or time intervals. Moreover, we assume that the data coming from sensors and measuring physical quantities are noise. For this purpose, we will modify the values and add or remove certain random values. This information is compared with the results coming from the digital twin.

To simulate faulty behaviour, we want also to introduce fault models into the Modelica models that can be switched on and off during operation. This allows for simulating failures that should be handled by the diagnostic system. For systems under operation we suggest making use of cyber-physical

systems like mobile robots or other systems that are available. AVL will support TUG in providing models that can be used for implementing a testing framework for the predictive maintenance system.

5.2.4 Implementation of a model-based predictive maintenance framework in the context of automated and autonomous driving (AVL)

Currently, most vehicles operate completely unobserved, which leads to no or just little available information on the system’s current state of health. Therefore, manual control intervals are required, and preventive maintenance work is carried out. However, between those inspection intervals, vehicle owners must accept the risk of sudden failure occurrence and unexpected system downtimes. The possibility to calculate the remaining lifetime of a system and to predicting faults in advance, would allow precise maintenance planning, increase the overall system availability, and reduce costs. Even more important, in the case of highly automated and autonomous vehicles, where sudden failures potentially result in catastrophic events, the implementation of a well-suited predictive maintenance framework could significantly contribute to enhance road safety.

Within AI4DI, a predictive maintenance framework is designed for automotive application that utilizes a combination of physical system knowledge and real-time vehicle data, to calculate the vehicle’s state of health and to predict the occurrence of failures in advance, as shown in Figure 31.

FIGURE 31 PROCESS OVERVIEW OF A REAL-TIME PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE FRAMEWORK FOR AUTOMOTIVE APPLICATION.

The process for such a predictive maintenance framework is described in the following. As an initial step, a comprehensive system analysis is carried out to identify potential failure parameters for vehicle components and subsystems. A failure parameter describes a specific failure mode (e.g. low cycle fatigue), its location (e.g. stator coils) and cause (e.g. mechanical load) and finally the resulting effects on system level (e.g. e-motor breakdown). Relevant failure parameters for a specific system are determined by applying suitable methods like root cause analysis (RCA) and failure mode and effects analysis (FMEA). In addition, failure parameters can also be obtained from reference driving cycles, where particular failures already occurred in the past during operation.

For the physics-based part of the predictive maintenance framework (indicated by the lower grey path), selected failure modes are described as physics specific and mathematical explicit damage models. In combination with the measured driving data, those models allow to calculate the aggregated degradation of a component or system and therefore its current state of health and the expected remaining lifetime.

The data-driven part of the predictive maintenance framework (indicated by the upper blue path), is designed to detect and predict failures that (i) originate from failure modes that cannot offhand be represented as damage modes (e.g. corrosion) or (ii) failures that are yet unknown but eventually occur during operation. Those unknown failures will increasingly affect the properties of components and systems, which is then reflected in the measured data (e.g. increasing vibrations or unusual

temperature rise). Once a new failure is detected, appropriate features are selected from the driving data to understand the behaviour of this failure and how it evolves. Subsequently, the data is used to train AI tools to predict the future occurrence of such failures.

6 Machinery Industry

6.1 Smart Robot with sensitive skin (TUD)

SC3 Machinery - Topic II: Smart Robot.

Partners: EDI (Lead), TUD, VIF, IMEC, VGTU (within this Deliverable only TUD participated)

Addressed Key Targets: 1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7

Addressed TRL Level: 4

Addressed AI Methods: Convolutional Neural Networks (NN) for object detection, NN using supervised learning, Inference on FPGA-based SoC, Automatic generation of synthetic training data, Augmentation of training data.

Addressed AI Attributes: Collaborative, transparent, safe, inclusive, integrative, reliable, resilient, verifiable.

Objectives and approach: Enable robots of any size to “feel” - a reflectometric sensor is proposed featuring miniaturized electronics and single-channel measurement also for large scale areas. Neural networks are used to map the sensor signal to the apparent deformation which is related to the touch input or collision event.

Demonstrator: Smart robot demonstrator with AI-based systems for manipulation with arbitrarily placed objects and intuitive human-machine interaction

Our primary goal is the identification of Touch and collision events which occurs on the skin of the robot. We used real world data generated by our partner Institute ILK, which have been measured by a *time-domain reflectometer* (TDR) device to train our machine learning models.

The process of learning was performed in the following order:

1. Firstly, pre-process the data using state-of-the-art signal analysis methods such as filtering, resampling, averaging in a set of measurements. We use different dimension reduction methods (PCA, IIR FILTER, Mutual information, Temporal CNN) to filter prominent features from the given data.
2. Secondly, Feature extraction: We use state-of-the-art deep learning models (DNN, CNN-LSTM, LOW PASS LSTM) for touch events detection.
3. Thirdly: We train the different deep learning models and compare the quality of the outcome by testing against withhold data sets.

The experimentation applied on the initial datasets depicts that by applying 1D Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) with recurrent neural network (RNN LSTM) the most promising results could be achieved, better than the other assessed state-of-the-art methods.

Based on this methodology we derived the following best practice for the given data set:

1. Pre-processing

We use the Moving Average Filter as a pre-processing method to remove the noise from the dataset.

2. Feature extraction

We use different feature extraction technique such as Principal component analysis (PCA), Infinite impulse response (IIR) low pass filter, Mutual information (MI), and temporal Convolutional neural

network (1D CNN). The purpose of all these methods is to reduce the space and time constraint for model training.

3. Model Training and Testing

We train state-of-the-art deep learning models (DNN, LSTM) on our TDR dataset for touch event detection. Firstly, we use a DNN method which detects the position and force of touch events. We use the Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) with Long-short term memory (LSTM) model due to the time domain nature of our dataset. LSTM is a dynamic neural network which trains the samples on different time steps. These models are implemented and trained by using the TensorFlow 2.0 framework. We have test data which used to check how well our model trained. We calculate the training, validation, and testing accuracy of a model and then analyse which model perform better than other state-of-the-art methods. The results show that 1D Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) with recurrent neural network (RNNLSTM) perform better than the other state-of-the-art methods.

To perform the needed workflow, we use: TensorFlow 2.0 and Keras as Simulation Framework

6.2 Learning systems distributed over computationally heterogeneous resources

6.2.1 Machine Learning for controlling work machines (VAISTO)

This chapter is intended to define an overall system design of simulating and automating industrial machine work cycles and mobility. This chapter presents simulation training and inference system design, solutions for transferring the architecture to the real world, use case specific prototype architectures and safety system designs.

For the real-world problems, it is often beneficial to train the reinforcement learning agent first in the simulation and then transfer it to the real world. Reinforcement learning agent training and inference system design is modular and should stay identical between the use cases. This way the same asset can be transferred to different use cases with only tweaking the hyperparameters and reward functions. Complexity of transferring the reinforcement learning agent to the real world depends largely on the task and the simulation environment. Still the same steps and designs can usually be followed to achieve the best results.

Vaisto focuses to simulate and prototype two use cases: digital twin machine work cycle automation and indoor logistics navigation, swarm intelligence and platooning. Digital twin work cycle automation concerns forest work machinery and their automation. The forest work machine needs to be able to drive and load and unload logs autonomously. This system is divided into two agent subsystems and master control. Master control oversees activating and using the agent subsystems for completion of the tasks. Both agent subsystems are trained independently on their specific task and have their own reinforcement learning models. In the indoor logistic swarm intelligence and platooning use case, warehouse robots need to learn to work together to complete various tasks inside the warehouse environment. The system architecture is close to the previously introduced use case except for the platooning agent. Platooning agent connects to the platooning follower through onboard peer-to-peer connectivity V2X-units and orders and moves two agents as one unit.

For the real-world applications with reinforcement learning agents, safety is a large concern. Since simulation environments are used to train and develop agents which are transferred to the real world,

the safety should be addressed in simulation as well. This chapter demonstrates two approaches to handle the safety issues, one for each prototype use case. First approach is a traditional deterministic safety approach. Deterministic safety system is a separate entity from the control application which is controlled by the agent and oversees the actions which agent is about to make. The Safety system oversees deterministically that the actions are safe to make, for example if the next action would lead to a crash it would intervene and prevent the crash. Deterministic approach is good for controlled environments that are well defined and known - such as a warehouse. Another approach to safety is to use the ReQueST method proposed by Deepmind. The ReQuest method evolves the reward function using human labelled state-action data and supervised learning so that the reinforcement learning agent learns to predict and does not need to explore unsafe states to find an optimal path.

This chapter is created within WP2 task 2.3 Hybrid intelligent system and subsystems level modelling and simulation and will provide input for SC3 and SC5. For this chapter, WP1 SC5 requirements were used as an input for simulation environment, scenario design and system architecture. The system architectures are designed to give a foundation for WP3.

Vaisto will use the results of this system design in WP3 task 3.1 Develop cognitive actuation, sensing and data acquisition components and IoT devices and task 3.2 Behavioural modelling of semiconductor components and IoT devices. The system design is used for data and reward modelling of reinforcement learning industrial machines. The design will also be used for data modelling and collection for platooning of the semi-autonomous vehicles.

In addition, the systems designed here will serve as a platform for developing WP4 task 4.5 embedded platform for integrating data mode inference operation and also integrate environmental sensors for data input vector generation. Lastly, it will provide an input for WP5 task 5.4 Machinery and industrial equipment and WP5 task 5.6 Transportation.

The overall reinforcement learning simulation system design is presented in subchapter 6.2.1.1. System integration and correspondence to the real-world scenarios is introduced in subchapter 6.2.1.2. Subchapter 6.2.1.3 focuses on use case specific systems and proposes different AI technology hybrids to handle the use cases as efficiently and confidently as possible. Subchapter 6.2.1.4 focuses on the safety aspects of using this technology and proposes different methods to handle this problem for different use cases.

6.2.1.1 Reinforcement learning simulation system design

In terms of machine learning, Vaisto focuses on reinforcement learning. Industrial machine work cycle development benefits greatly from reinforcement learning and simulation reducing the time and cost while enabling the automation of complex problems.

This chapter presents overall simulation system architecture for training and inference of the reinforcement learning agent. This subchapter introduces chosen tools and justifications for using these tools.

Training is a vital part of reinforcement learning and needs to always be done before inference. Because training takes a large amount of time and energy, it is best to be done inside a simulation environment in a sustainable and accelerated way using the right tools. Before the agent can be deployed to the real-world scenario it needs to be validated with inference in the simulation environment to ensure confidence and generalization.

6.2.1.1.1 Training

Training is done inside customized the Unity environment [15]. The Unity environment needs to be customized for each use case and contain as much visual and physics randomization as possible. It has been researched that with maximum and automatic randomness of the simulation environment, the reinforcement learning agent learns to generalize and can adapt to more unforeseen situations [99]. System diagram for the training of the agent is presented in Figure 32.

FIGURE 32 TRAINING SYSTEM CONTEXT DIAGRAM

Unity was chosen as a simulation tool for its support for machine learning, simulation and highly scalable simplistic physics engine. Unity provides a toolkit called ML-Agents for connecting and training the reinforcement learning agent [100]. Unity allows customization of the environment, physics and controls to any degree. Subsystems inside Unity reinforcement learning training simulation are presented in Figure 33.

FIGURE 33 TRAINING CONTAINER DIAGRAM

The Python ML-agents reinforcement learning toolkit is an external program which connects to the Unity environment. This makes the Unity environment and ML-agents easily changeable in a case that use case has some specific needs. ML-agents reinforcement learning toolkit produces TensorFlow Protobuf graph as well as Unity Inference model of the trained agent.

Training can be done on any PC or mac with a decent amount of power. Although it is recommended for the hardware to have powerful GPU and CPU to speed up the training to decent times.

6.2.1.1.2 Inference

It is important to validate the model after training using a simulation environment after the training to confirm the confidence of the model and avoid real world safety problems.

The validation inference is done using Unity Inference engine and works out-of-the-box with the model produced in the training phase. The system design diagram is shown in Figure 34.

FIGURE 34 SIMULATION INFERENCE SYSTEM CONTEXT DESIGN

It is vital that simulation environment inference corresponds to the real-world inference as closely as possible. By doing so, the simulation produces transferable models.

The simulation will differ from the real world due to different constraints such as computing power and simplifications of the controls and physics. The differences and constraints need to be known and addressed for each use case.

6.2.1.2 Real world reinforcement learning system design

The simulations have become more realistic and closer to the real world, but still there are differences and issues in transferring the model from the simulation to the real world. This subchapter defines the architecture for the system running in the edge computing device in the real scenario and addresses potential problems and solutions with it.

6.2.1.2.1 Inference

In the simulation environment, all controls, environment, and sensors are defined and modelled inside the simulation environment making it easy to parse and get exact information for the observations. In the real world this is usually not the case since sensor data can include noise and unexpected variables. Real world systems also include random delay due to distributed and heterogeneous computing environments.

Therefore the simulation should produce as generalized model as possible with high tolerance for changing environment and noise. Reinforcement learning agent models produced by simulation environments can be converted and transferred to almost any edge computing hardware.

The software and hardware are chosen according to the use case. Container diagram is presented in Figure 35.

FIGURE 35 REAL WORLD EDGE INFERENCE CONTAINER DIAGRAM

As seen in Figure 35 the edge system consists of 3 different subsystems which receive input from the sensors. Control application is the master application which processes the data received from the sensors and agent and transfers processed input and output to right modules.

Agent uses the neural network model produced in the simulation environment to make decisions based on observations received from the control application. Control-by-wire subsystem oversees controlling the physical properties of the industrial machine, for example joint positions, steering and throttle.

Hardware depends a lot for each use case: how much external power e.g. vibrations it needs to endure, how much computing power is needed and what kind of safety cases are related to the use case. Needed computing power is determined mainly by the capacity demand of sensor processing and complexity of the neural network. Prototypes can use for example Raspberry PI and Intel Movidius Neural Compute Stick. For increased endurance and reliability suitable industrial computer should be used.

6.2.1.2.2 Additional training

In an ideal case the simulation model could work out-of-the-box in the real world, but often this is not the case. In such a case the model needs to be fine-tuned for the real world.

For the training, a more powerful computer is needed since usually the edge computing devices are not powerful enough for training the model. Also, other resources like electricity, fuel, human effort,

and other materials needed in the process, would be wasted in real-world training. System architecture for training is presented in Figure 36.

FIGURE 36 REAL WORLD TRAINING

The simulation model should be as close as possible to the real model so the need for additional training is minimal or non-existent because real world training can be thousands of times slower than simulation training.

Training in the real world also raises serious safety issues since the reinforcement learning agent could potentially need to explore new unsafe states. Safety issues are presented and addressed in subchapter 6.2.1.4.

6.2.1.3 Use case specific system-design

The architecture can be very different for different use cases due to the diversity of the tasks and control schemas. Basic architecture and relations of training and inference with the reinforcement learning agent stays the same but the environment, controls and tasks may vary greatly.

Vaisto focuses and presents system architecture for two use cases: digital twin work cycle automation and indoor logistics swarm intelligence with platooning.

In these cases, usage of the hybrid AI technologies is essential. The system architectures combine reinforcement learning models with deterministic AI and supervised learning models when applicable. The case architectures are designed and prototyped in a simulation.

6.2.1.3.1 Digital twin work cycle automation

Digital twin work cycle automation consists of two different tasks: loading/unloading logs and driving a predefined route.

The architecture consists of three main systems: master control system, log loader system and driving system. System architecture design container diagram is presented in Figure 37.

Note that agents and neural network models are shown as their own entities for the clarity of the AI hybrid architecture even though in reality they are embedded in the control subsystems.

The simulation of this system is done using Unity and suitable extension modules.

FIGURE 37 RIGITAL TWIN WORK CYCLE AUTOMATION SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE DESIGN

As seen in Figure 37, the system uses three different neural networks to achieve various tasks as efficiently as possible.

Master control application uses deterministic AI to control and order the agent applications to run and work when they are needed.

Log loader control application uses an agent which receives information about the log from 3D-object detection model trained with supervised learning to recognize log pose and 3D-position using RGB-D camera.

Driving control application uses a driving agent which receives RGB-image directly from the frontal camera to make decisions based on the visual observations and GPS position.

In the real world these subsystems can reside in different edge computing devices to ensure modularity, reliability, safety, and efficiency. Same edge computing systems as described in subchapter 6.2.1.2.1 can be used.

Figure 38 presents the hardware setup for this use case.

FIGURE 38 DIGITAL TWIN WORK CYCLE AUTOMATION HARDWARE

6.2.1.3.2 Indoor logistics swarm intelligence and platooning

The environment in this use case is a warehouse where warehouse worker robots need to move heavy items from point A to point B for further processing.

The task can be divided in 2 subtasks: finding a way to the item and carrying the item. The prototype warehouse has short items and long items. For the long items it is essential for two warehouse robots to communicate and cooperate with each other to complete the task.

For these tasks, the robots need to find a way to intelligently work together to avoid collisions and ensure efficiency. In this use case, the system uses the same master control architecture as the digital twin work cycle system introduced in subchapter 6.2.1.3.1.

The system design is presented in Figure 39. Note that agents and neural network models are shown as their own entities for the clarity of the AI hybrid architecture even though in reality they are embedded in the control subsystems.

The simulation of this system is done using Unity and related extension modules.

FIGURE 39 INDOOR LOGISTICS SWARM INTELLIGENCE AND PLATOONING SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE CONTAINER DIAGRAM

Warehouse robots use LIDAR-sensors to observe their surroundings and receive information from the mission planning system about their tasks and local positions. Mission planning system is a separate entity which decides deterministically which robots are assigned which tasks. It can deliver messages, for example, over the local wireless network. The purpose of the path finding control application is to utilize the path finding agent to find the optimal path to the target destination. Path finding agent uses two different neural network models for path finding: path finding while carrying an object and while not carrying an object.

The models are divided because these two cases require different behaviour and are most reliably achieved by dividing the models. When two warehouse robots start carrying a long item, platooning mode is activated. In platooning mode, one robot takes the role of leading vehicle and sends commands and directions to the other robot via peer-to-peer connectivity V2X-unit.

The follower robot listens and executes actions according to the broadcasted messages from its platooning leader, while broadcasting its own position for safety and behaviour optimization. Platooning leader utilizes a platooning agent to get actions for the robot pair.

As for hardware, edge computing devices can be the same as presented in subchapter 6.2.1.2.1 using LIDARs and a commercial indoor tracking system such as ultra-wideband positioning as sensors. If an indoor tracking system is not suitable or applicable, simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) could be used to map the area and then retrieve the position. The network and indoor tracking needs to have low latency (< 2ms) and high accuracy (< 10cm). The simulation environment needs to simulate these inaccuracies and noises. Hardware system design is presented in Figure 40.

FIGURE 40 INDOOR LOGISTICS SWARM INTELLIGENCE AND PLATOONING HARDWARE DESIGN

6.2.1.4 *Safety subsystem design*

When using reinforcement learning agents in real machines it is important to design the safety approach. To prototype scenarios there are currently two viable options: separate deterministic safety system and Deepmind ReQueST [101]. Both are good alternatives for different scenarios and should not be dismissed without proper inspection.

For indoor logistics swarm intelligence and platooning scenario, the deterministic safety system is the most simple and most functional approach. Deterministic safety system is preferably a completely external application residing on its own safety compliant container that checks that the actions of the agents are within the safety boundaries.

For warehouse robots this would mean that before making an action the external program checks that executing the action does not lead to collision based on the sensor data. If it does lead to collision, the safety system overrides the control application and resets, shuts it down and potentially performs action to stop any motion. The warehouse environment is isolated, and it is assumed that there are not too many unexpected variables so the cases for safety are easily identified.

The digital twin work cycle automation use case needs a more complex system since the forest environment is highly unstructured and uncontrollable and there are too many variables for example

rocks, humans, undrivable terrain and other obstacles to be identified deterministically. Deepmind's ReQueST method introduces a reinforcement learning agent that can predict unsafe states without exploring them. The workflow for ReQueST is presented in Figure 41.

FIGURE 41 IEQUEST WORKFLOW

The concept is to train a separate reward model using supervised learning, generative models and expert labelled data. The generative model generates possible extreme and problematic trajectories inside the simulation environment which then experts label with neutral, positive or negative reward.

The reward model is then trained using supervised learning and trained data. After this the agent is trained inside simulation using the trained reward model as a reward function.

The research shows that the agent learns to predict unsafe states and does not visit them. In the digital twin use case this is essential especially when using the agent in the real world. In conclusion, the agent learns to generalize and identify the unsafe states.

6.2.1.5 Contribution to overall picture

This chapter provides identification of the tools for using reinforcement learning for automation of the industrial machines in a simulation and in the real world. The report also identifies tools for simulating work machines and platooning. The report also presents a concept solution for integrating AI methods with simulation and control modelling.

This chapter introduces AI hybrid intelligent systems for indoor warehouse worker swarms and digital twin work cycle automation.

AI hybrids use a combination of supervised learning, deterministic AI and reinforcement learning to adapt to specific use cases.

The system designs cover overall reinforcement learning, two specific use cases and safety design. The safety system can use one or two different methods to ensure the safety of the AI machine using reinforcement learning.

6.2.1.5.1 Relation to the state-of-the-art and progress beyond it

This chapter describes systems that use state-of-the-art for industrial automation tasks. The progress beyond is achieved by validating and using the given methods and tools for various real-world purposes. Table 7 lists the state-of-the-art research and describes how it is used and validated.

TABLE 7 RELATION TO STATE-OF-THE-ART

Partner/Topic	Description
RL autonomous control hybrid [1]	OpenAI Solving Rubik's Cube with a Robot Hand uses AI hybrid to recognize the next move for the hand and then uses reinforcement learning for autonomous control. This chapter described the same process for industrial context and uses a real use case.
Unity simulation reinforcement learning [2]	Unity ML-agents have been used in many examples to play and solve games, but it has sparse to none written papers and examples for simulating a real world use case and transferring the model to the real machine. This chapter proposed pipelines and architectures for both of the cases.

6.2.1.5.2 Impacts to other WPs, Tasks and SCs

As described in subchapter 6.2.1, this chapter will be used as an input for next work packages and tasks done by Vaisto. Table 8 lists the Tasks and work packages that are impacted by topics.

TABLE 8 IMPACTED WPs AND TASKS

Topic	Description
RL industrial digital twin	SC3, SC5 - WP3 task 3.2, WP4 task 4.5, WP5 task 5.4
RL platooning	SC3, SC5 - WP3 task 3.1, WP5 task 5.6

7 Food and Beverage Industry

7.1 Food production - Soya Beans (SINTEF, IGT, NXTECH)

The activities focus on the exploration of various ways to combine and integrate different AI technologies and provide software tools identification and concept solution for integration of AI methods on modelling, simulation, and design.

The AI techniques and methods for soybeans food production addresses two main areas: The optimisation of the production and the maintenance processes.

The optimization of parameters in the industrial application employed make use of AI methods such as pattern identifications for activity recognition and perception for experience-driven sequential decision-making. Furthermore, this supply chain focus on the implementation part, and these methods are to be integrated with actions concerning the real manufacturing environments and real-time monitoring with industrial IoT and edge distributed intelligence.

7.1.1 Production process optimization use case

The production process optimisation use case is based on data collected by industrial IoT sensors/cameras and analysed using AI algorithms to improve the utilization of the raw material, increase the yields and end-product quality by supporting and/or replacing manual work and existing systems. Another important factor is to optimize the energy consumption.

The overall target is a learning system that monitors the production line and recommend/execute production adjustments when needed to preserve or increase the quality and utilization. The production line stage equipped with industrial IoT sensors/cameras is identified by a vulnerability analysis based on years of experience, available historical data, means tests, expected effect, etc.

The AI algorithms are fed with collected data from sensor/camera sources in a specified time interval and edge computing are implemented when appropriate. Typical parameters monitored are temperature, moisture, colour, dimensions, weight, volume, etc.

7.1.2 Predictive maintenance use case

The predictive maintenance of the production machinery use cases are based on data collected by industrial IoT sensors and analysed using AI algorithms to identify abnormalities and potentially breakdown situations.

Depending on the identified issue, necessary action shall be carried out (adjustment, service, repair, replacement, etc.) to avoid further deterioration and/or uncontrolled downtime in the production line. The overall target is a learning system that monitors a normal state and gives alarm in the event of an abnormal state.

The machinery equipped with industrial IoT sensors is identified by a vulnerability analysis based on years of experience, available historical data, means tests, expected effect, etc. The AI algorithms are fed with collected data from sensor sources in a specified time interval and edge computing are implemented when appropriate.

Typical parameters monitored are temperature, vibration, pressure, sound/noise, frequency, current/voltage, etc.

7.1.3 Sub-system level modelling and simulation for integration of AI methods

The successful use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the use cases rely on the development of well-defined models, simulations and algorithms, and the capability of handling stochastic elements. Seamless integration and connectivity are required between all relevant parts of the sub-systems involved in the use cases.

Modelling a well-defined model representing each use case challenge is important for successful simulations. The algorithms analyse the incoming data in combination with historical data regarding the specific use cases and its requirements. The learning algorithms are built upon more simple algorithms in the bottom and execute training scenarios are necessary to full fill these complex algorithms. The digital twin concept is based on virtual representation of physical objects or sub-systems in the plant and will be a part of the use case training and analysis.

Real-time data streams from the sensors etc. will be used to continuously update the digital twin representation and turned into useful information at an early stage (diagnostics, predictions, warnings, actions, etc.). Distributed intelligence through Edge computing is an important integration part of including AI methods, as well as take part in reducing latency and the amount of data to be transferred. Integrating AI methods requires connectivity between all relevant parts of the sub-systems involved in the use cases.

FIGURE 42 WORKFLOW AND IMPLEMENTATION BLOCKS

The different communication paths must match the amount of data and latency needed for the specific tasks, and the following wireless protocols have been identified and distributed on the different use cases according to relevant properties: Wi-Fi, LoRa, WirelessHART, and Bluetooth (Figure 42). The use case solutions will to a large extent rely on edge computing, However, central data power (e.g. ROMEO) will be used for training the AI tool with respect to machine learning. The results can then be transferred back to edge devices for further use.

Smart factory is introduced in Industrie 4.0, where cyber-physical systems monitor the physical processes of the plant and make decentralized decisions [102].

The physical systems become connecting IoT devices and are cooperating with each other and with the employees. For a plant or system to be considered Industry 4.0, it must include the following criteria [102]:

- **Interoperability** between machines, devices, sensors, and employees that connect and communicate with one another.
- **Information transparency** by the system creating a virtual copy of the physical world through sensor data to contextualize received information.
- **Technical assistance** includes both the ability of the systems to support employees in making decisions and solving problems and the ability to assist employees with tasks that are too difficult or unsafe for employees.
- **Decentralized decision-making** includes the ability of cyber-physical systems to make simple decisions on their own and become as autonomous as possible.

In both use cases we want to predict the future based on collected data and act accordingly, whether it applies on the final quality of soya beans or the machinery uptime. The combination of AI and M2M communication facilitate a data-driven approach where the decentralized decision-making is carried out without or with minimal human intervention.

8 Transportation Industry

The AI4DI Supply Chain 5 about transportation (SC5 Transportation) is intended to show how AI solutions would help Mobility as a Service (MaaS) operators to turn automated driving into optimised fleet management. The demonstrations focus on selected key enablers for automated MaaS services.

A central case is how passengers switch between the bus and automated taxi. Thereby, two levels of MaaS are investigated. On the one hand, small-scale operations involving the real-world test fleet and the developed algorithms to implement the safe switch of the passengers in multi-modal transportation system are demonstrated. On the other hand, upscaling operations and optimisation MaaS algorithms on city-level that inhere higher complexity are not feasible to conduct in the real-world yet. Thus, the simulation environments described in this section will be leveraged for enabling AI research on fleet operations and data processing for these scenarios.

8.1 Mobility-as-a-Service / Development of the artificial intelligence based fleet management for supporting multi-modal transport

Simulations within are equally important for AI-based MaaS development as are tests with real vehicles and sensors. They have the various benefits for automated MaaS research:

Collision-related safety of automated vehicle algorithms is practically mandatory to test first in simulated scenarios, before moving on to road tests and simulations can augment test cases for dangerous and highly complex scenarios, which are difficult to test otherwise. Due to their repeatability of the scenarios, they enable the iterative development of algorithms which clear benchmarks for their performance. This is not possible when relying solely on measured data since the actuation e.g. for the path planning cannot be fed back.

Today's automated vehicle prototypes are generally not yet able to cover full cities – rather they operate on a set of routes – therefore, wide-scale future effects on transport system and MaaS must be simulated. Besides this current technical limitations, also economic factors encourage the use of simulations, because the long-time operation of automated vehicle fleets is also very expensive as it requires human safety drivers. They allow to run more tests and kilometres driven in the same time at lower cost. However, it must be underlined that this does not mean that real-driving test are negligible, but rather finalizes the whole testing process after proving the correctness and performance of the algorithm in the simulation.

In context of ML algorithms, simulation provide additional benefits. For instance, they enable AI training techniques such as reinforcement learning. Thereby, the training for automated driving algorithms, e.g. collision avoidance, cannot be employed using real vehicles due to safety and economic reasons. Instead, collisions are detected in the simulation and a negative feedback is given for every collision to improve the reinforcement model.

In addition, simulation inhere the information of the ground-truth of the whole system (with regards to the simulation limitations, e.g. the underlying physics). Thus, they can be leveraged to generate additional training data for supervised learning and allow to determine the model behaviour with increasing uncertainty, e.g. when only a portion of the simulation is observable for an agent due to its (virtual) sensor restrictions.

To cover various aspects of automated MaaS, the simulation architecture, depicted in Figure 43, is chosen. It consists of five building blocks, each addressing different facets:

FIGURE 43 SIMULATION COMPONENTS

Simulation of Urban Mobility (SUMO): The open source tool SUMO, initially released by the German Institute of Transportation Systems in 2002, will be employed to model the road network and traffic demands of large real-world scenarios (city-level) in a microscopic way. It offers an extensive interface Traffic Control Interface (TraCI) to observe all simulated elements including vehicles, pedestrians and traffic lights and predefines the mobility of each node on an integrated routing engine. In addition, it offers openness to other simulation environments, e.g. OMNet++, which focusses on communication channel modelling.

Unity3D: Unity simulation engine will be used as the main digital twin environment and visualisation technology in SC5 demo use cases. Unity platform provides near photorealistic graphics and flexible technology integration possibilities [15]. It can integrate road traffic generation, autonomous vehicle control applications and AI-driven smart traffic services.

Automated Vehicle Scenario Simulator (AVSS): VTT's in-house software that has various features. It is especially used for analysing and developing automated vehicle logic for different traffic scenarios. It can simulate the decisions and movement of several automated passenger cars and buses at a time, including pre-programmed movement of other road users such as other cars, roadworks, traffic lights, pedestrians etc. The simulation uses real automated vehicle algorithms – although, there are several optional algorithms.

MaaS: The MaaS component represents a proxy for all further data processing and interaction with the simulation environment on global level (fleet routing). Thereby, it uses virtual sensor inputs obtained from the simulation stack to feed its algorithms. It further orchestrates computation on the Intelligent Transportation System (ITS) testbed hardware at the edge and utilizes the Data Fusion Bus (DFB) for processing the data in the cloud.

Simulation Mediator: The synchronization of the data of the simulation stack (SUMO, Unity3D and AVSS as shown in Figure 44) and MaaS platform is handled by a dedicated mediator component. It is divided into three sub-system, handling the data flow and the task dispatching.

FIGURE 44 REPRESENTATION OF INTERSECTION IN DIFFERENT SIMULATION ENVIRONMENTS (RUSKO, FINLAND)

8.1.1 Microscopic simulation architecture design for scaling MaaS use cases (OTH)

This subsection describes the architecture design of a microscopic simulation for automated MaaS with a focus on mobility and data processing partitioning aspects.

MaaS encloses versatile computation units, reaching from low-powered IoT to edge device up to high performance computers in the cloud. These components are connected by various communication channels including on-board bus systems (CAN/LIN/FlexRay), Ethernet, Wi-Fi (IEEE 802.11x) and cellular network (Long-Term Evolution (LTE)). Thus, it is challenging to find an optimal solution to employ a resource efficient task pipeline in this constantly changing network. This problem is investigated by leveraging simulation environments, capable of reflecting the microscopic (each vehicle and its dynamics are modelled individually) mobility and the computational properties of the tasks while respecting the limitations of the processing hardware nodes at the same time.

The architecture of the simulation environment comprises two steps. First, the mobility of the processing nodes (vehicles) will be designed. Based on these generated scenarios, networks and their connections to the infrastructure are determined and transferred to a hardware testbed which serves as a basis for the partitioning and scheduling of the task pipeline.

The topic addresses the subsystem of data processing within MaaS and with a focus on offloading of tasks to edge devices, preferably on the infrastructure side to reduce the limited on-board power consumption. Algorithms for online partitioning and scheduling will utilize RL approaches to optimize the underlying planning problem. SUMO will be used as a basis for node mobility and connectivity estimation. Benchmarks on the ITS testbed is leveraged to retrieve an abstract computation model which finally is harnessed to test the performance of the partitioning algorithms.

8.1.1.1 Mobility Simulation

Scaling mobility simulation is one necessary building block for various subtopic within the SC5. It will be used as an environment for testing fleet management operations and – the major focus for OTH’s investigations - to generate network models based on the vehicle mobility. Several existing simulations meet the requirements defined in D1.13. These solutions include commercial software such as PTV Vissim [103] and open-source software such as MATSim [104] and SUMO [105].

In AI4DI, the following arguments led to the use of SUMO over alternatives:

- openness (published under Eclipse Public License v2)
- capability to simulate upscaling road networks including infrastructure and vehicle objects
- the access to simulations meta information using the extensive Traffic Control Interface (TraCI) and the variety of additional extensions (e.g. emission and fuel consumption calculation) implemented by the community
- enables to simulate interactions between different simulation objects (vehicles, pedestrians, bus, and infrastructure) and even multi-modal traffic scenarios

To include other simulation aspects, focussing e.g. on the underlying computation platform per road user or 3D environment models, this simulated can be augmented by connecting SUMO to other simulators via the TraCI interface as described in Section 8.1. In a similar manner, the telecommunication network channel estimation is added by transferring the mobility scenario generated by SUMO to the Veins/OMNet++ environment [106].

Simulation Setup

FIGURE 45 SUMO SIMULATION ENVIRONMENT AT TAMPERE FOR FLEET OPERATION OPTIMIZATION

The SC5 consortium agreed on two areas (Tampere City Centre and Rusko) of interest for all research activities in AI4DI. Consequently, it is necessary to model these areas in SUMO. The road network is based on OSM map data, whereas recorded real measurements of the accessible infrastructure (traffic cameras and loop sensors) are harnessed to generate a realistic traffic demand model. For the latter, SUMO already provides various algorithm implementations (ACTIVITYGEN, FLOWROUTER, DFROUTER, JTCROUTER, Cadyts [107]) to generate and calibrate traffic demands using these traffic density metrics, but struggle when the locations of the sensors is rather low [105].

In AI4DI, it will be investigated whether reinforcement learning techniques are applicable as well to create an even more realistic traffic demand model. Therefore, the recordings of traffic cameras (about one image per minute) are leveraged. Novel object detection models (YoloV3) are harnessed to determine traffic demand metrics (pedestrians, vehicles, traffic lights) as a pre-processing step. As a next step, time series prediction models are trained per traffic camera to anticipate the traffic density metrics. Finally, RL is applied using the SUMO environment and performing actions (spawning vehicles and setting their origin and destination) by an agent using the TraCI interface.

The reward function will be based on the accuracy of the generated traffic demand within SUMO at the camera locations with regards to their corresponding trained time-series model.

8.1.1.2 Testbed for analysis of distributed processing pipelines

New partitioning and scheduling algorithms for deploying task directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) to heterogeneous platforms as part of the research in AI4DI. Therefore, the applicability of RL-based approaches, as illustrated in Figure 46, is investigated, which implies to generate an appropriate environment to run the computations. The following hybrid approach is conducted to ensure accuracy of the simulation as well as repeatability of the experiments.

FIGURE 46 REINFORCEMENT LEARNING APPROACH FOR TASK SCHEDULING

Hardware-in-the-loop approach: using versatile hardware platforms introduced in D2.2 (NVIDIA Jetson *, Coral Board), the ITS testbed, illustrated in Figure 47, is developed. Its purpose is the execution of the dispatched application-related task dependency graph. This approach has several benefits. On the one hand, it will simplify the integration to the real-world MaaS application since the utilized platform remain the same. On the other hand, it is a mandatory prerequisite for creating an accurate virtual representation of the processing environment. Running benchmarks on the target platforms (e.g. using either generic or application-related processing tasks) create the parameter that are required to calibrate a pure virtual simulation environment. Required monitoring techniques to obtain these parameters are described in D2.2 (Power and Performance monitoring in SC5).

FIGURE 47 CONCEPT FOR MODULAR HARDWARE-IN-THE-LOOP ITS TESTBED

Virtual simulations - a digital twin for elaborating computation aspects: the acquired parameters are harnessed to calibrate SimGrid [108], which provides models and APIs to simulate popular distributed computing platforms. As an input, it requires an abstracted representation of the processing network (platforms and channel modelling) and of the computation tasks.

Using this setup, new algorithms can be implemented and easily compared to existing algorithms, e.g. the Heterogeneous Earliest Finish Time (HEFT) algorithm.

The presented hybrid environments will be used to develop partitioning and scheduling algorithms using RL. Thereby, the agent will perform valid DAG operations, as described in [109]. The environment

responds with updated state as well as the corresponding state (placement of the tasks in the network) and reward (overall makespan, throughput of messages energy consumption of the task processing pipeline). In addition, the reality-gap between the real-world ITS testbed and its digital twin can be verified and creates an iterative process to optimize the calibration process.

The generic testbed for task processing as described in the previous paragraph will be further augmented by MaaS-related knowledge.

Based on the mobility model (Subsection 8.1.1.1), only a portion of the devices of testbed is available for the ego-vehicle. Accordingly, these platforms will be allocated and used to calculate the optimal scheduling (Figure 48). In addition, also the tasks processing graph can change according to the vehicle position.

FIGURE 48 SUMO MOBILITY MODEL DEFINES THE PROCESSING NETWORK

8.1.2 3D-Simulation environment based on Unity for MaaS (VAISTO)

This subtopic introduces the 3D-simulation environment design and architecture used for simulating realistic 3D traffic for the MaaS use case. The 3D-simulation environment is designed as an independent Unity application.

The Unity application offers interfaces to publish traffic information from the SUMO simulation and to subscribe for realistic 3D-traffic camera images simulated from the published SUMO data. The overall 3D-simulation environment sub-system architecture and responsibilities of the containers are shown in Figure 49.

FIGURE 49 UNITY 3D-SIMULATION ENVIRONMENT CONTAINER ARCHITECTURE FOR THE MAAS USE CASE

The designed system has two major subsystems: message interface and highly optimized entity component system. Message interface is responsible for trafficking the incoming and outgoing data and messages.

The Entity Component System is responsible for the 3D-simulation environment providing rendering for the cameras, containing the traffic entities, and performing calculations.

FIGURE 50 REAL-WORLD VS UNITY-ENVIRONMENT PRELIMINARY COMPARISON

Both systems are designed to run safely and independently in separate threads to avoid locking each other. Furthermore, the entity component system uses multi-threaded data-oriented technology stack making the rendering and algorithms performant with massive real-time data flow. Preliminary comparison between the modelled Unity 3D-Environment and the real-world traffic camera picture is presented in the Figure 50.

9 Conclusion

9.1 Contribution to the overall picture

The AI4DI project addresses the needs of European societies, economies, and industries to successfully adopt new data-based methods. We firmly believe that the gap in digitisation between Europe and industrial nations like the US and China can be explained by the lack of successful integration rather than by a lack of knowledge or ingenuity. Within T2.3, our consortium worked closely together to discuss the latest methods and simulation techniques. This report reflects the summary of these endeavours and emphasises the ongoing transfer of advanced technology from research to industry, paving the way for new products, business ideas and more efficient processes.

Note that we see all Key targets of AI4DI well covered in this report and hence are confident being aligned with the overall direction/vision in the project (Heterogeneous Control, Homogenous Control, Human-Machine collaboration, Change & Anomaly Detection, Distributed System Intelligence, AI Tools and Methodology, IoT Devices)

The task leaders of T2.3 would like to thank all the authors of this report for their fruitful collaboration and are firmly convinced that the results of task 2.3 point in the right direction in terms of the overall vision. Furthermore, we believe that strong communication undertaken is a decent cornerstone that will lead to fruitful cooperation in the further course of this project.

9.2 Impacts to other WPs and Tasks

It is worth noting that T2.3 strongly depends on the overall vision and the roadmap that is identified in WP1. Especially the determined industrial requirements from Tasks 1.2-1.6 were necessary to develop the in this report proposed toolchains on the system and sub-system level in an industry-relevant way. Moreover, simulation and modelling identified in this report are integrated into the high-level architecture in T2.1 (Reference hybrid system-level architecture). Moreover, T2.2 (Hybrid system and sub-systems, HW/SW logic/knowledge partitioning and design) is defining the system-level architecture for HW/SW partitioning where the proposed simulation and modelling methodologies of this report are classified in the scope of edge, edge-to-cloud, cloud.

As already reflected in the introduction, simulation-based approaches are a cost-efficient way to achieve AI applications that might lead to business-relevant products. From this perspective, solutions developed in T2.3 might be a good starting point for business cases that are subject of T7.2 (Business cases and exploitation plans for AI technologies and applications in digitising industry).

The critical point of simulations that usually simplify the real-world needs to be reconsidered in WP6 (Validation, Verification and Test) to guarantee methods that are valid and can safely be employed in industrial environments. Note that the integration requires the safe and certified operation that is subject of T7.3 (Standardisation), where standardisation purposes will pave the way towards industrial adoption.

Many toolchains presented in this report employ specialised hardware like GPU clusters. These prerequisites need to be analysed in T2.4 (System-level platforms simulation and integration) as well as WP5 (Integration and Deployment of AI Applications in Industry) in order to specify how the solutions can ultimately be integrated (e.g., by employing cloud resources).

Finally, it is worth noting that simulation usually creates appealing video footage that might serve as media for dissemination and communication in the context of T7.1 (Dissemination and Communication).

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